

TwINSol-CECs International Conference on Environmental and Sustainable Research Solutions

Book of abstracts

University of Novi Sad
Faculty of Technology Novi Sad
Novi Sad, Serbia

June 5-7, 2025

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

TwINSol-CECs International Conference on Environmental and Sustainable Research Solutions

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia,
June 5-6, 2025

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Dear colleagues,

It is a great pleasure to welcome you to the **International Conference on Environmental and Sustainable Research Solutions**, the final conference of the **TwINSol-CECs project**. We are honored to host this event organized here in Novi Sad, by the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, bringing together a diverse and inspiring group of researchers, experts, and project partners, who share a common commitment to advancing scientific knowledge in support of a more sustainable future towards a toxic-free environment.

This event marks the culmination of the TwINSol-CECs project, which has, over the past years, contributed significantly to strengthening research capacities of the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad in domain of environmental research, enhancing the international cooperation of our researchers, and promoting innovative approaches in the field of Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs). Building on the success of the 1st and 2nd TwINSol-CECs Workshops held in 2022, and 2024, this final conference is envisioned as our most ambitious event, both in scope and in outreach.

As part of the conference, the **3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop** is held with the aim of presenting the TwINSol-CECs project's infrastructure and research. This includes showcasing the technical resources acquired through the project, as well as the project research activities carried out at the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad. The workshop is also intended as a platform for networking and fostering new collaborations, while raising awareness about the capabilities and resources available at our institution for future joint scientific endeavors.

In this spirit of collaboration and knowledge sharing, we are proud to host a joint session with the FERTILEAVES project (HUSRB/23S/11/027, Interreg VI-A IPA Hungary–Serbia Programme), and its 2nd Workshop, recognizing the importance of amplifying the impact of both initiatives. This joint session reflects our shared dedication to addressing environmental and sustainable challenges, and gathers the oral presentations oriented towards biotechnology-driven research solutions. It also serves as a strategic step toward more effective dissemination of the project results and broader visibility of the achieved outcomes.

We hope the conference program is dynamic enough to inspire the exchange of research ideas, challenge established perspectives, and foster new collaborations in the pursuit of cleaner technologies, healthier ecosystems, and a resilient, sustainable future.

We thank all participants for joining this triple event, and we wish that it will be a productive and inspiring gathering of researchers with memorable and meaningful networking.

Co-Chairs

Prof. Zita Šereš, Dr. Jelena Živančev, and Prof. Nataša Đurišić Mladenović

PROGRAM

TwINSol-CECs International Conference on Environmental and Sustainable Research Solutions, June 5-7, 2025

with satellites

3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop, June 5-6, 2025

**2nd FERTILEAVES Workshop “Sustainable Solutions Through Biotechnological Approaches”,
June 5, 2025**

Organized by

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad (FoTNS), Serbia

PROGRAM

Thursday, June 5, 2025

Venue: Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Vojvodina, Braće Popović 5, Novi Sad

9.30-10.30 Registration

10.30-10.45 Welcome and opening speeches by the Conference Co-Chairs,
Zita Šereš, Acting Dean, TwINSol-CECs Project Manager for Strategic Issues, FoTNS
Jelena Živančev, FERTILEAVES Coordinator, FoTNS
Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, TwINSol-CECs Coordinator, FoTNS

TwINSol-CECs and FERTILEAVES Joint Session: Environmental and Sustainable Solutions Through Biotechnological Approaches

Session Chairs: Csaba Vágvölgyi and Jelena Živančev

Plenary lecture

10.45-11.15 Phytomicrobiome as the source of beneficial bacteria and fungi for the alleviation of drought stress in agricultural crops

László Kredics, Orsolya Kedves, Tamás Marik, Csaba Vágvölgyi

Department of Biotechnology and Microbiology, Faculty of Science and Informatics, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary

Oral presentations

11.15–11.30 Innovations in climate-resilient crop breeding

Aleksandra Radanović, Sandra Cvejić, Dragana Rajković, Boško Dedić, Biljana Kiprovska, Maja Tanasković, Miloš Krstić, Jelena Ovuka, Sonja Gvozdenac, Sonja Tančić-Živanov, Nemanja Čuk, Verica Zelić, Dušan Dunderski, Jelena Jocković, Milan Jocković, Milan Miroslavljević, Siniša Jocić, Goran Bekavac, Ana Marjanović-Jeromela, Ankica Kondić-Špika, Dragana Miladinović

Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Novi Sad, Serbia

11.30-11.45 Sunflower under stress: sustainable breeding solutions for drought adaptation and nutrition quality improvement
Sandra Cvejić, Boško Dedić, Aleksandra Radanović, Nada Grahovac, Milan Jocković, Nemanja Čuk, Jelena Jocković, Sonja Gvozdenac, Srđan Bursać, Siniša Jocić, Dragana Miladinović, Vladimir Miklič
Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Novi Sad, Serbia

11.45-12.00 Refreshments

Oral presentations

12.00-12.15 Development of biorational methods for seed protection during storage against biotic and abiotic stressors
Sonja Gvozdenac¹, Jelena Ovuka¹, Miloš Krstić¹, Aleksandra Ilić¹, Nevena Nagl¹, Dušan Stanislavljević¹, Aleksandra Nastasić¹, Vladimir Miklič¹, Milica Škorić¹, Dejan Prvulović², Radenka Kolarov², Snežana Tanasković³, Dušan Marković³, Zagorka Lozanov-Crvenković⁴
¹Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Novi Sad, Serbia
²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Novi Sad, Serbia
³University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Agronomy, Čačak, Serbia
⁴University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia

12.15-12.30 Bioactive ecdysteroid analogues: cinnamate esters and *tert*-butyl oxime ethers with antitrypanosomal properties
Márton Háznagy¹, Máté Vágvölgyi¹, Gábor Girst¹, Sandhya R. Krishnan², Kaushavi Cholke², Jürg Gertsch², Attila Hunyadi^{1,3}
¹Institute of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
²Institute of Biochemistry and Molecular Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland
³Interdisciplinary Centre for Natural Products, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary

12.30-12.45 Protoflavonoids: Exploring the non-tumor-related bioactivities of a rare group of natural products
Máté Vágvölgyi¹, George Anis Al-Qassab¹, Gábor Girst¹, Gabriella Spengler², Attila Hunyadi^{1,3}
¹Institute of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
²Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunobiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
³Interdisciplinary Centre for Natural Products, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary

12.45-14.00 Lunch break

Oral presentations

14.00-14.15 Tracking Emerging Contaminants in Soil: Integrating pollutant analysis into FERTILEAVES pilot study
Dušan Rakić, Igor Antić, Maja Buljovčić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, Jelena Živančev
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

14.15-14.30 Innovative *Bacillus*-based technology for plant growth promotion and yield enhancement in sweet potato farming
Ádám Bordé-Pavlicz¹, Tamás Monostori², László Kredics¹, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović³, Jelena Živančev³, Csaba Vágvölgyi¹
¹Department of Biotechnology and Microbiology, Faculty of Science and Informatics, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
²Institute of Plant Sciences and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Szeged, Hódmezővásárhely, Hungary
³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

14.30-14.45 The potential of digestate- and *Bacillus*-based circular soil amendment to enhance early tomato development,
Tatjana D. Dujković, Ivana S. Danilov, Vanja R. Vlajkov, Jovana A. Grahovac
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Novi Sad, Serbia

14.45-15.00 Coffee break

TwINSol-CECs Session: Environmental Research Solutions
Session Chairs: Marinella Farre and Zita Šereš

Plenary lecture

15.00-15.30 From data to action: advancing water treatment and monitoring with AI
Claudia F. Galinha
LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Caparica, Portugal

Invited lectures

15.30-15.50 Degradation of bioplastics and related compounds in a conventional WWTP process by activated sludge
Marta Llorca¹, David Alcaide-Benavides^{1,2}, Eloy Torres¹, Marinella Farré¹
¹ON HEALTH Research Group, Environmental Chemistry Department, IDAEA-CSIC, Barcelona, Spain
²Doctoral Programa in Analytical Chemistry and Environmental Science, Dep. Of Chemical Engineering and Analytical Chemistry, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

15.50-16.10 Embracing circular economy principles in wastewater treatment: by-products from the food industry as effective biosorbents for pollutant removal
Natalija Velić¹, Marija Stjepanović¹, Marta Ostojčić¹, Darko Velić¹, Janez Gorenšek², Sandra Budžaki¹
¹University of Osijek, Faculty of Food Technology Osijek, Osijek, Croatia
²IAMB-Institute for Applied Mycology and Biotechnology, Celje, Slovenia

13.00-17.00 **3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop - TwINSol-CECs capacities and results - interactive session with project teams**

Due to the relocation of the event from Faculty of Technology Novi Sad to the Vojvodina Chamber of Commerce and Industry, visits to the TwINSol-CECs laboratories will be replaced by a dedicated interactive session where participants can meet the research teams, discuss the capacities of the laboratories in front of the poster presentations on the equipment and project research activities.

Friday, June 6, 2025

Venue: Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Vojvodina, Braće Popović 5, Novi Sad

- 10.30-11.00 Registration
- 11.00-13.30 **Joint poster session of the TwINSol-CECs Conference and the 3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop**
(set-up Friday, June 6, 10.30-11.00, dismantling on Friday, June 6, 16.30-17.00, or Saturday, June 7, 12.45-13.30)
- 13.30-14.30 Lunch break

TwINSol-CECs Session: Environmental Research Solutions
Session Chairs: Marta Llorca and Igor Antić

Plenary lecture

- 14.30-15.00 Micro- and nanoplastics: from the environment to humans
Marinella Farré, David Alcaide, Eloy Torres, Xavier Borrell, and Marta Llorca
On-Health Research group, Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research (IDAEA), CSIC, C. Jordi Girona, 18-26, Barcelona, 08034, Spain

Invited lecture

- 15.00-15.20 Wide-scope screening of emerging contaminants and their transformation products in wastewaters by using liquid chromatography high-resolution mass spectrometry
Dimitra A. Lambropoulou^{1,2}
¹Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece
²Centre for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI-AUTH), Balkan Center, Thessaloniki, Greece

- 15.20-15.35 Coffee break

Invited lecture

- 15.35-15.55 PFAS from useful chemicals to environmental hot topic - solving the (bio)degradation puzzle
Vladimir Beškoski
University of Belgrade – Faculty of Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia

Oral presentations

- 15.55-16.10 Passive but promising: passive sampling of per- and polyfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAS) in wastewater
Kristina Mraz¹, Antonin Halek ¹, Veronika Svobodova ¹, Vaclav Janda ¹, Jana Pulkrabova ¹, Jakub Hejnic ², Martin Srb ², Darina Dvorakova ¹, Vojtech Kouba ¹
¹ University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Prague, Czech Republic
² Prague Water Supply and Sewerage Company, Prague, Czech Republic
- 16.10-16.25 Mitigating transport of ionizable organic pollutants in alluvial soils using biochar
Tamara B. Apostolović¹, Marijana M. Kragulj Isakovski¹, Marko D. Šolić¹, Jelena M. Beljin¹, Irina B. Jevrosimov¹, Snežana P. Maletić¹
¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

- 16.25-16.40 **Biomonitoring of non-occupational arsenic exposure among advanced lung cancer patients in Vojvodina**
Nataša Milošević¹, Danica Szadanić-Velikić², Mirjana Ševo^{3,4}, Danijela Lukić⁵, Maja Milanović¹, Nataša Milić¹
¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia
²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Clinic for Pulmonary Oncology, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia
³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia
⁴IMC Banja Luka-Center of Radiotherapy, Part of Affidea Group, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
⁵Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

- 13.30-17.00 **3rd TwINSol-CECs Workshop - TwINSol-CECs capacities and results - interactive session with project teams**

Saturday, June 7, 2025

Venue: Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Vojvodina, Braće Popović 5, Novi Sad

- 9.30-10.00 Registration

Session: Environmental Research Solutions

Session Chairs: Claudia Galinha and Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović

Keynote lecture

- 10.00-10.45 **Confronting the threat of TFA and other persistent and mobile substances to protect water resources**
Hans Peter H. Arp^{1,2}
¹ Norwegian Geotechnical Institute (NGI), Oslo, Norway,
² Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Trondheim, Norway

Invited lecture

- 10.45-11.05 **Carbon based amendments advancing sustainable solutions for contaminated environmental matrices**
Snežana Maletić, Jelena Beljin, Irina Jevrosimov, Tamara Apostolović, Srđan Rončević, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

- 11.05-11.20 Coffee break

Oral presentations

- 11.20-11.35 **Comparative life cycle assessment of sewage sludge management options in Serbia**
Ferenc E. Kiss¹, Djurdja V. Kerkez², Milena R. Bečelić-Tomin², Anita S. Leovac Maćerak², Vesna Ž. Pešić²
¹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia
² University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia
- 11.35-11.50 **UV/Chlorine process for degradation of Ibuprofen and Trimethoprim in aqueous solutions**
Anett Čović, Luca Farkas, Teodóra Dragić and Tünde Alapi
Department of Molecular and Analytical Chemistry, University of Szeged, Hungary

- 11.50-12.05 From capture to destruction: a two-step concept for PFOA remediation in aqueous systems
Kristina K. Kasalica¹, Marija M. Lješević¹, Bojana B. Marković¹, Nenad N. Radić¹, Jelena J. Radulović³, Vladimir V. Beškoski²
¹University of Belgrade - Institute for Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Njegoševa 12, Belgrade, Serbia, *kristina.kasalica@ihtm.bg.ac.rs
²University of Belgrade – Faculty of Chemistry, Studentski trg 12-16, Belgrade, Serbia
³Anahem LTD, Belgrade, Serbia
- 12.05-12.20 The investigation of the radical set in persulfate ions assisted heterogeneous photocatalysis
Bence Veres, Tünde Alapi
Department of Molecular and Analytical Chemistry, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
- 12.20-12.35 Investigation of the efficiency of melamine-modified biochar-based photocatalysts in Persulfate-based AOPs for Trimethoprim Degradation
Dinesh Chandola¹, Gabor Varga², Zsuzsanna László³ and Tünde Alapi¹
¹Department of Molecular and Analytical Chemistry, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
²Department of Physical Chemistry and Material Science, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
³Department of Biosystem Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Szeged, Szeged, Hungary
- 12.35-12.45 Conference closing remarks
- 12.45-13.30 **TwINSol-CECs networking session with refreshments: Future Project Endeavors**

Poster presentations

- P1** PHENOL REMOVAL FROM WATER USING FIR BIOWASTE-DERIVED PYROCHAR,
Aleksandra Adamović, Mirjana Petronijević, Saša Savić, Sanja Panić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
- P2** SUSTAINABLE PHYTOREMEDIATION AND BIOFUEL PRODUCTION USING BRASSICA NAPUS ON MULTI-CONTAMINATED SEDIMENTS,
Ana Marjanović Jeromela, Željko Milovac, Snežana Maletić, Nadežda Stojanov, Nina Đukanović, Stanko Milić, Srđan Rončević, Jelena Beljin, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Tijana Zeremski
- P3** EVALUATION OF NANOFILTRATION MEMBRANE MATERIAL IMPACT ON THE REMOVAL OF PHARMACEUTICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS,
Jelena Šurlan, Nikola Maravić, Zita Šereš, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Claudia Galinha, Carla Brazinha, Joao Crespo
- P4** METHYLENE BLUE REMOVAL FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION USING HYDROCHARS DERIVED FROM PEACH AND APRICOT POMACE,
Danijela Stefanović, Marija Miladinović, Marija Tasić, Milan Kostić, Biljana Đorđević, Olivera Stamenković
- P5** SOLVENT-ASSISTED METHANOLYSIS OF WASTE POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE,
Anita Jović, Milan Kostić, Farzam Fotovat, Marija Miladinović, Biljana Đorđević, Olivera Stamenković
- P6** KINETICS OF QUICKLIME-CATALYZED METHANOLYSIS OF HEMP SEED OIL,
Milan Kostić, Biljana Đorđević, Marija Miladinović, Olivera Stamenković
- P7** DEVELOPMENT OF RENEWABLE POLYURETHANE BIOCOMPOSITES FOR WASTEWATER TREATMENT,
Milan Nikolić, Slobodanka Stanojević-Nikolić, Vladimir B. Pavlović

- P8** PINWOOD-BASED B-DOPED PYROCHAR WITH ENHANCED SURFACE AFFINITY FOR CATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN,
Sanja Panić, Nebojša Vasiljević, Mirjana Petronijević, Jelena Živančev, Igor Antić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
- P9** UTILIZATION OF POULTRY WASTE AS A NATURAL BIOSORBENT FOR Cu²⁺ REMOVAL,
Sanja Petrović, Saša Savić, Bratislav Todorović, Staniša Stojiljković
- P10** BIOCATALYTIC PHENOL DEGRADATION USING PEROXIDASE EXTRACTED FROM CABBAGE LEAF RESIDUES,
Saša Savić, Sanja Petrović, Jelena Mitrović, Mirjana Petronijević, Marcela Barbinta-Patrascu
- P11** REMOVAL OF PHENOL FROM WATER USING ACTIVATED CARBON OBTAINED FROM *S. cerevisiae* BIOMASS,
Slobodanka Stanojević-Nikolić, Milan Nikolić, Marina Šćiban, Vladimir Srdić, Vladimir Pavlović
- P12** DEVELOPMENT OF A LOW-COST ZEOLITE COMPOSITE FILTER FOR ARSENIC REMOVAL FROM WATER,
Vesna Vasić, Ivan Stijepović, Dragana Lukić, Marija Milanović
- P13** AGOSERV PROJECT – A UNIQUE PLATFORM FOR SUPPORTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS AND FOSTERING AGRO-ECOLOGICAL TRANSITION,
Ankica Kondić-Špika, Dragana Trkulja, Svetlana Glogovac, Igor Vukelić, Dragana Miladinović, Ana Marjanović Jeromela
- P14** SUSTAINABLE DAIRY INNOVATION THROUGH THE VALORIZATION OF SAGE (SALVIA OFFICINALIS) BY-PRODUCTS: TOWARD FUNCTIONAL FOODS,
Dajana Vukić, Mirela Iličić, Maja Bjekić, Katarina Kanurić, Branimir Pavlić, Jovana Degenek, Vladimir Vukić
- P15** ZnCrAl LDH BASED MIXED OXIDE AS PHOTOCATALYST FOR WASTEWATER REMEDIATION,
Đurđica Karanović, Milica Hadnadjev-Kostic, Tatjana Vulic
- P16** MERCURY EXPOSURE: EVIDENCE FROM A BIOMONITORING STUDY IN WOMEN UNDERGOING IN VITRO FERTILIZATION,
Maja Milanović, Marko Ilinčić, Jana Pavlović, Nataša Milošević, Artur Bjelica, Nataša Milić
- P17** BIODEGRADABLE PROTEIN-BASED FILMS INCORPORATED WITH RUTIN AND RUTIN/β - CYCLODEXTRIN COMPLEX,
Mina Bosnić, Željana Radonić, Jelena Ostojić, Jelena Milinković Budinčić, Jadranka Fraj, Lidija Petrović, Sandra Bučko, Jaroslav Katona
- P18** THE INFLUENCE OF KOMBUCHA INOCULUM ON ACIDIFICATION PROCESS, QUALITY OF FRESH CHEESE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY OF PRODUCTION
Mirela Iličić, Maja Bjekić, Katarina Kanurić, Vladimir Vukić, Dajana Vukić, Jovana Degenek
- P19** INSECT FARMING BYPRODUCTS AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOURCE OF CHITOSAN,
Željana Radonić, Jelena Milinković Budinčić, Lidija Petrović, Matija Milković, Tea Sedlar, Danka Dragojlović, Jadranka Fraj, Sandra Bučko, Jaroslav Katona, Mina Bosnić, Jelena Ostojić, Ljiljana Spasojević

- P20** BORON-DOPED BIOCHAR AS AN EFFICIENT ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL OF SELECTED CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN FROM WASTEWATER,
Nebojša M. Vasiljević, Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Taciana Guarnieri, João Sérgio, Geórgia Labuto, Vanessa Pereira, Joao Crespo, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
- P21** AFLATOXINS IN SERBIAN MAIZE: THE URGENT NEED FOR INTEGRATED RESPONSES TO CLIMATE CHANGE,
Jovana J. Kos, Bojana Đ. Radić, Radmila O. Radović
- P22** REMOVAL OF BISPHENOL A FROM WATER: CARBON-BASED ADSORBENTS, MECHANISMS, AND TREATMENT EFFICIENCY,
Marija Šobić, Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
- P23** POTENTIAL OF LIGNIN AS AN ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL AND DETECTION OF HORMONES FROM WATER,
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Bojan Miljević, Vesna Miljić, Ivana Danilov, Jovana Grahovac, Siniša Markov, Snežana Vučetić

KEYNOTE LECTURE

Hans Peter Arp, PhD, is a Professor at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology and Norwegian Geotechnical Institute.

His research interests are at the intersection of fundamental and applied aspects of environmental pollution. On the fundamental level, he is interested in how different types of pollutants, such as microplastics, PFAS, PAHs, POPs, and metals behave in the environment. On the applied level, he uses this fundamental knowledge to design solutions within the context of emerging technologies and policy mechanisms, such as REACH and the circular economy, to create a zero-pollution society. His research projects include SLUDGEFFECT, which seeks to mitigate the harmful presence of hazardous substances of sewage sludge and e-waste plastic within a circular economy, ZeroPM (Zero Pollution of Persistent, Mobile Substances), which involves 16 institutes across Europe identifying ways to prevent, prioritize and remove the pollution of mobile PFAS and other PMT/vPvM substances, and ARAGORN (Achieving Remediation And GOVERning Restoration of contaminated soils Now), with the goal of developing guidance to accelerate the safe remediation, restoration, and rehabilitation of soils contaminated with PFAS, organochlorine/bromine contaminants, petroleum-coal, and metals.

KEYNOTE LECTURE

CONFRONTING THE THREAT OF TFA AND OTHER PERSISTENT AND MOBILE SUBSTANCES TO PROTECT WATER RESOURCES

Hans Peter H. Arp^{1,2}

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Water resources worldwide, even in remote locations, have become increasingly contaminated with substances that are considered persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) or very persistent and very mobile (vPvM). This concern has recently led to PMT/vPvM substances being added a new category of hazardous substances the European regulation for Chemical, Labelling and Packaging (CLP, (EC) No 1272/2008) in 2023, as well as plans to add it to the REACH regulation (1907/2006/EC). PMT/vPvM substances are those which do not break down easily in the environment (persistent), are transported rapidly in the water cycle (mobile) and are in some cases toxic. They are associated with widespread, negative effects on the environment and human health, as well as with expensive clean-up costs. Advanced water treatment methods, like ozonolysis or activated carbon filtration, are generally ineffective. This has led to several civil and legal disputes regarding them, as it is not always clear who should pay for their large remediation costs.

An exemplary case of a PMT/vPvM substance is trifluoroacetic acid (TFA). TFA is one of the ultrashort-chain perfluoroalkyl acids, a subset of the larger family of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). TFA is a degradation product of many refrigerants, pesticides and pharmaceuticals and is also directly released from industrial products and processes; it is now widespread and increasing rapidly in water resources. TFA has been assumed to be of little concern, in part because it was not able to bioaccumulate; however, the ubiquitous accumulation in the environment, in particular its observed accumulation in water resources and in various plants, including crops, is causing concentrations in human blood to increase with time. Recent levels in many regions have exceeded recommended exposure thresholds. Concerns of TFA include liver toxicity, toxicity to reproduction and the slowing of respiration rates in microbial communities. This irreversible increase of TFA can be considered a planetary boundary threat, based on increasing exposure world-wide, irreversible environmental contamination, and long-lasting disruptive effects on human health and vital earth system processes. At the end of the presentation solutions will be provided on how diverse actors can work together to phase out the sources of TFA and other PMT/vPvM substances, on a pathway towards zero pollution.

Keywords: water pollution, PMT substance, PFAS, TFA, transformation products

Acknowledgements: This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036756 – ZeroPM.

PLENARY LECTURES

László Kredics, PhD, graduated as a molecular biologist at the University of Szeged in 1996.

As an Associate Professor, he is recently the head of the Research Group of Environmental Microbiology and Biological Control at the Department of Biotechnology and Microbiology of the University of Szeged. In the course of his work, he is selecting strains capable of biological control against plant pathogenic microorganisms and of plant growth promotion. He assembles synthetic communities and tests them *in vitro*, in plant growth chambers, greenhouses, and open field experiments. In recent years, he coordinated the development of several microbiological inoculants for agricultural purposes, one of which was recognized with the Southern Great Plain Innovation Award in Hungary. As an expert of the filamentous fungal genus *Trichoderma*, he was the first in Hungary to survey the green mold disease in the cultivation of champignons and oyster mushrooms, and to report on the appearance of the North American biotype of mushroom green mold (*Trichoderma aggressivum*) in Europe. He successfully isolated and tested bacterial strains suitable for biological control in mushroom cultivation and increasing crop yield. With his research group he enriched the knowledge available on peptaibols - non-ribosomal peptides produced by *Trichoderma* species - by discovering several new peptaibol families. He also confirmed the role of numerous fungal species in corneal infections and participated in the scientific description of new fungal species isolated from special habitats. Ten PhD students have successfully defended their dissertations under his supervision. In addition to his research work, he teaches a series of courses in Hungarian, English, and German language. He has contributed to the publication of a total of 142 scientific journal articles, 22 book chapters, 26 conference proceedings, and about 400 conference abstracts, with a cumulative impact factor above 330, a number of independent citations above 4300, and a Hirsch Index of 38. He is a member of the Microbiology Committee of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences and the Presidency of the Hungarian Microbiological Society.

PLENARY LECTURE

PHYTOMICROBIOME AS THE SOURCE OF BENEFICIAL BACTERIA AND FUNGI FOR THE ALLEVIATION OF DROUGHT STRESS IN AGRICULTURAL CROPS

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Phytomicrobiome – also known as plant microbiome - is considered to be the second genome of the plants. This term encompasses a characteristic community of microorganisms that occupy a well-defined habitat with distinct physio-chemical properties, along with the spectrum of activities exerted by them. The phytomicrobiome consists of multiple parts, including the rhizosphere microbiome, the endosphere microbiome, the phyllosphere microbiome, the seed microbiome and the anthosphere microbiome.

Drought stress is a consequence of climate change that has substantial negative effects on agricultural plants. Drought is influencing not only the plant but also its phytomicrobiome by changing the composition of both bacterial and fungal communities. Furthermore, drought influences the plant-microbe interactions through structural and biochemical changes of the rhizosphere (increase in root depth, root density and the amount of root exudates) as well as through changes in the composition of microbial communities.

Phytomicrobiome engineering is a complex activity aimed at changing the phytomicrobiome to increase the proportion of beneficial microorganisms like plant growth promoting bacteria (PGPB) and fungi (PGPF). A well-engineered phytomicrobiome is expected to ensure biological control of plant diseases, to promote the utilization efficiency of essential elements like nitrogen, phosphorous and iron, to increase plant growth and productivity, as well as the tolerance of the plant to abiotic stress effects, including those resulting from low water availability. Microorganisms use various morpho-physiological, biochemical and molecular mechanisms for drought stress alleviation. PGPBs may improve the soil structure, phosphorous solubilization, biological nitrogen fixation, proline accumulation, exopolysaccharide production and 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate (ACC) deaminase activity, increase the uptake of water and nutrients, as well as elevate the leaf water potential and the production of plant hormones (auxin and cytokinin). PGPFs may promote plant growth, induce systemic resistance to pathogens, and exert biocontrol activities by competition, antibiosis and mycoparasitism. A special group of fungi, the arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) have the potential to osmotically adjust the plant, increase its gas exchange, regulate plant genes, protect the plant against oxidative damage, efficiently increase the uptake of water and nutrients, and beneficially modify the root morphology and the soil.

By the isolation, identification and detailed physiological characterization of drought stress alleviating bacteria and fungi and the assemblage of synthetic communities from them we could develop microbial inoculants applicable for soil, seed, leaf or flower treatments to help agricultural crop plants in counteracting the negative effects of drought.

Keywords: drought stress, phytomicrobiome, stress alleviation, plant growth promotion

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Hungary–Serbia IPA Cross-border Co-operation Programme (project FERTILEAVES, HUSRB/23S/11/027).

Claudia Galinha holds a PhD in Chemical and Biochemical Engineering (2012) and is currently Assistant Researcher at the Associated Laboratory LAQV-REQUIMTE, NOVA University Lisbon.

Her work is focused on the use of advanced mathematical tools applied to (bio)chemical and separation processes aiming to deliver novel and innovative solutions to optimise biological and chemical production, and optimise separation and purification processes. She has experience in water treatment systems using different membrane processes, monitoring of biological and chemical systems, as well as in monitoring fouling formation, and in the development of soft sensors. Since her PhD, she participated in 17 funded R&D projects, 11 International and 6 National, being the principal investigator of her institution in 5 European projects and in 2 National projects.

PLENARY LECTURE

FROM DATA TO ACTION: ADVANCING WATER TREATMENT AND MONITORING WITH AI

Claudia F. Galinha

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Water treatment systems are increasingly challenged by increasing environmental pressures, complex contaminant profiles, and the need for real-time operational efficiency. In this context, Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers powerful tools to enhance both process modeling and monitoring capabilities, leading to processes' optimization. Artificial Intelligence can support water treatment systems in several key areas: process modeling and optimization, fault detection and diagnosis, predictive maintenance, and the creation of soft sensors that infer critical parameters from indirect measurements. These data-driven approaches complement traditional mechanistic models, offering greater adaptability to changing conditions and improved performance in complex or data-scarce environments. Moreover, AI enables more efficient monitoring and control strategies by identifying patterns that are difficult to detect with conventional methods.

In this work, it is demonstrated the application of AI techniques (ranging from machine learning models to soft sensors development) in various water treatment contexts. At municipal wastewater treatment plants, machine learning models were developed to predict effluent and influent quality based on online parameters (e.g. temperature, pH, conductivity) and absorbance spectroscopy, allowing the development of soft sensors that can be integrated on-line in an IoT platform for process monitoring, supporting real-time process adjustments. In the petrochemical industry, AI-driven tools were used to model and monitor high-load, variable wastewater streams, enhancing treatment reliability. Finally, for the removal of micropollutants, machine learning was used to assess the phenomena underlying the removal of compounds from water in a nanofiltration process, based on molecular descriptors.

These case studies illustrate the versatility and potential of AI in addressing both operational and environmental challenges in water treatment, laying the foundation for more autonomous, resilient, and sustainable water treatment systems.

Keywords: machine learning, water treatment, soft sensors

Marinella Farré, PhD, is a research Professor at the Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research from the Spanish Research Council (IDAEA-CSIC), Spain.

Her main research interest is the occurrence, fate, and behaviour of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) in the environment, their transfer to the food chain, and their impact on the environment and human health. To this end, the group she leads is focused on developing analytical methods based on liquid and gas chromatography coupled to high-resolution mass spectrometry (GC/LC-HRMS) combined with biological techniques. These investigations have been funded through 43 national and international research projects. Her leadership roles included coordinating the FP7-OCEAN-2013-1/Sea-on-a-Chip GA 614168, the JPI FOREWARN (2021-2024), and currently the ONE-BLUE project HE-101134929 (2024-2017). Dr. Farré is a co-author of more than 220 peer-reviewed papers, 29 book chapters, and co-editor of 2 books. According to Google Scholar, she received more than 17,000 citations, H-index 76.

PLENARY LECTURE

MICRO- AND NANOPLASTICS: FROM THE ENVIRONMENT TO HUMANS

***Marinella Farré**, David Alcaide, Eloy Torres, Xavier Borrell, and Marta Llorca**

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Microplastics (MPLs <1 mm) and nanoplastics (NPLs <1 μm) are increasingly recognized as emerging environmental pollutants with potential ecological and human health implications[1]. They originate from the breakdown of larger plastic items (secondary plastics) or are manufactured intentionally for use in products (primary plastics), such as cosmetics, industrial abrasives, and biomedical applications. Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPLs) have been detected in **all environmental compartments**[2-5].

The extent of the widespread, planetary contamination by plastic waste is difficult to capture fully. NPLs are currently at the centre of research concerning plastic litter, both for the analytical challenges they pose and their potential to provoke hazardous effects in organisms. However, there are still many unanswered questions in this multidisciplinary field, with a crucial missing piece being the quantification of NPLs. In this sense, new analytical methods for assessing MNPLs are needed.

In this presentation, new approaches based on size exclusion liquid chromatography coupled to high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC(SEC)-HRMS) and pyrolysis gas chromatography with high resolution mass spectrometry (Py-GC-HRMS) for quantifying polymers and additives of MNPLs occurrence in the environment and biota[2, 6], as well as new approaches for assessing the main routes of human exposure and accumulation[1], will be discussed.

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INVITED LECTURES

Marta Llorca, PhD, Tenured Scientist at the Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research (IDAEA) belonging to the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) (Spain) and one of the group co-leaders of the ON HEALTH research group.

Currently, her research deals with the development of new methodologies for the analysis of micro- and nanoplastics based on conventional fuel-based and bio-based polymer plastics and other (polar)organic emerging contaminants from anthropogenic sources in the environment by means of LC-HRMS and GC-HRMS; to develop laboratory studies for elucidating the origin and fate of selected contaminants including degradation and transformation processes. She has participated in different research projects and nowadays is developing the investigation within the national project BIOplasticMENT and the EUprojects TwINSol-CECs, PARC, Plastic Pirates, ONE-BLUE and Urban M2O. Her research yielded 83 scientific papers in SCI journals from the first quartile and H-Index of 41 (2008-2024), 9 book chapters and she has participated in more than 45 national and international conferences.

INVITED LECTURE

DEGRADATION OF BIOPLASTICS AND RELATED COMPOUNDS IN A CONVENTIONAL WWTP PROCESS BY ACTIVATED SLUDGE

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The use of plastics is a global environmental concern problem where a promising solution is the use of bioplastics, produced from renewable sources such as starch or corn, that can be biodegraded under different conditions [1]. However, it is not clear how they are degraded in waste water treatment plants (WWTPs). In addition, it is necessary to evaluate the possible leaching of plastic additives added in bioplastics, used to provide them with specific resistance or malleability, and their subsequent possible elimination or transformation. We evaluated the elimination of (bio)microplastics, leaching of plastic additives and related compounds and their further elimination facilitated by conventional activated sludge (CAS) organisms. For doing so we exposed the material for 15 days at laboratory scale, aerating daily, emulating day/night periods and monitoring the pH and temperature. Commercial garbage bags made of polylactic acid (PLA), as an example of biopolymer, were fragmented to microsize and exposed to CAS. In parallel, PLA micropellets were also exposed to biodegradation.

The extraction and purification of plastic additives was carried out by solid phase extraction while the extraction of (bio)plastics was done by filtration with 0.7 μm glass fiber filter and subsequent extraction with toluene and facilitated by ultrasonic assisted extraction [2]. The analyses were done using suspect screening strategies. In the case of plastic additives, the analysis was done by means of LC-ESI-HRMS and data was acquired in full scan at resolution of 70,000 FWHM and data dependent scan in parallel. On the other hand, the analysis of fuel-based (bio)plastics was carried out SEC-APPI-HRMS while PLA analyses were done by means of pyrolysis-GC-HRMS QExactive.

The data generated for plastic additives was processed by means of Compound Discoverer software decreasing the confirmation level from 5 up to 1 in the case of 22 commonly added plastic additives. The results showed that, for example, PLA garbage bags leached abietic acid, tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate, linoleic acid and Uvinul® 3049 which increased along the experimental time denoting a constant leaching through all the experiment. In the case of bioplastics, an elimination c.a. 98% of the PLA garbage bag was observed, where microorganisms can use it as a source of energy, facilitating the hydrolysis of PLA into LA monomers and further metabolized.

Keywords: bioplastics, waste water treatment plant, biodegradation

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Natalija Velić, PhD, full professor, graduated from the Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology at the University of Zagreb with a degree in Biochemical Engineering and earned her PhD in Biotechnology from the same faculty in 2010.

Since graduation she has been employed at the Faculty of Food Technology Osijek, University of Osijek initially as an assistant and later as a professor. She teaches biotechnology-related courses across all levels of study (Basics of Biotechnology, Biotechnology in Food Production, Basics of Bioprocess Engineering, Bioprocesses in Environmental Protection, Wastewater Treatment Processes). She currently serves as the head of the interdisciplinary doctoral program Nature and Environmental Protection. Her research focuses primarily on fermentation technology and the application of biotechnological and engineering principles to environmental protection. In particular, her work explores the use of food industry by-products as biosorbents for the removal of pollutants from wastewater. Her scientific bibliography comprises 40 articles indexed in relevant databases (WoSCC-SCI-Exp, WoSCC-ESCI, Scopus, CAB), and 10 book chapters. She has participated as a researcher in several national and EU-funded projects.

INVITED LECTURE

EMBRACING CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRINCIPLES IN WASTEWATER TREATMENT: BY-PRODUCTS FROM THE FOOD INDUSTRY AS EFFECTIVE BIOSORBENTS FOR POLLUTANT REMOVAL

Natalija Velić^{1*}, Marija Stjepanović¹, Marta Ostojčić¹, Darko Velić¹, Janez Gorenšek², Sandra, Budžaki¹

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In recent years, increasing attention has been directed toward the transition to a sustainable and circular economy in the food industry, driven by its substantial resource demands and the high generation of production residues, including by-products, some of which are repurposed, while much is still discarded or incinerated. The circular economy model promotes the use of various production residues as valuable resources, thereby reducing environmental impact and enhancing sustainability. This work explores the feasibility of repurposing by-products and waste from the food industry as affordable alternatives for removing different pollutants from wastewater. Due to its high efficiency, ease of implementation, and ability to remove a wide range of structurally diverse pollutants, adsorption is frequently employed in real wastewater treatment systems. For this purpose, activated carbon or other highly effective and well-characterized conventional adsorbents are most commonly utilized. However, they are often associated with high production costs and resource-intensive manufacturing. Extensive research is therefore being conducted on the potential application of food industry by-products, as low-cost, environmentally sustainable non-conventional adsorbents. When these adsorbents are derived from biological materials, they are commonly referred to as biosorbents. The efficiency of different biosorbents originating from the food industry - namely brewers' spent grains, hazelnut shells, buckwheat hulls, grape seeds, eggshells, and waste mushroom biomass - for the removal of synthetic dyes, nutrients (N and P), and pharmaceuticals from water will be discussed. Furthermore, various modifications (physical, chemical or biological treatments) of these materials to enhance their adsorption properties and improve their effectiveness in removing pollutants from water will also be discussed.

Keywords: circular economy, food industry byproducts, biosorption, pollutants removal, wastewater

Dimitra Lambropoulou, PhD, is Chemist and a Professor on Environmental Chemistry in the Environmental Pollution Control Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH).

She is a member of the ENVIGREEN group of the Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation (CIRI) of AUTH. Her main research interests are the development and application of novel sample preparation techniques coupled to advanced mass spectrometry approaches in the field of environmental chemistry, design and application of new materials in analytical and separation sciences, occurrence, transport, fate and effects of emerging contaminants (endocrine disruptors and pharmaceutical products, illicit drugs, polar pesticides, transformation products, nanomaterials and microplastics) in the environment (in waste and natural water), identification and structure elucidation of organic contaminants by high resolution mass spectrometry, application of “omics” techniques (Suspect Analysis & Non Target Analysis) to environmental problems, wastewater-based epidemiology. She is also interested in the development of effective degradation and purification processes for the mineralization of organic micropollutants such as Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs). She has published more than 250 ISI papers (plus 2 books and 18 book chapters) that have received more than 11800 citations (Scopus, h index 60). She serves as Associate Editor for the journal *Science of Total Environment* and as editor in the journals *Total Environment Advances* and *Current Opinion in Environmental Science & Health*. She has been included in the list of World Top 2% Scientists for 2019-2024 which is compiled by the Stanford University (USA) based on standardized citation indicators.

INVITED LECTURE

WIDE-SCOPE SCREENING OF EMERGING CONTAMINANTS AND THEIR TRANSFORMATION PRODUCTS IN WASTEWATERS BY USING LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY HIGH-RESOLUTION MASS SPECTROMETRY

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The total number of chemicals with the potential to enter the environment remains largely unknown, presenting substantial challenges for both environmental scientists and analytical chemists. Traditional analytical approaches for detecting emerging contaminants (ECs) in environmental matrices typically focus on a limited set of target analytes, thereby failing to capture the full spectrum of potentially hazardous substances. The emergence of high-resolution accurate mass spectrometry (HRMS) has substantially advanced analytical capabilities, enabling the comprehensive detection, characterization, and identification of a wide range of organic compounds in complex environmental matrices. As a result, environmental monitoring is progressively shifting from conventional target-based methodologies to more powerful strategies such as suspect screening analysis (SSA) and non-targeted analysis (NTA). These advanced approaches utilize accurate mass measurements, fragmentation pattern analysis, and retention time data—primarily obtained via liquid chromatography coupled with high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS)—to facilitate the detection, characterization, and identification of both known and previously unrecognized contaminants. The present study focuses on a wide-scope target, suspect and non-target screening of ECs and their transformation products into wastewaters (Wastewater Treatment Plant, Thessaloniki). An in-house database composed of > 1000 compounds was established, and SSA & NTA workflow was optimized and applied to determine the presence of micropollutants in surface waters and wastewaters. In total over 70 micropollutants & their TPs were detected in the analyzed samples, including pharmaceuticals, personal care products, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances and other persistent industrial chemicals. To support effective environmental management, a prioritization strategy was developed to identify key contaminants that could pose significant risks to water ecosystems. This study highlights the advantages of suspect and non-target screening methods in capturing a wide array of micropollutants in environmental samples and emphasizes their potential to support the integrated management of contaminants by leveraging insights into shared transport dynamics and transformation processes within aquatic systems.

Keywords: LC-HRMS, micropollutants, transformation products, waters, wastewaters

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Vladimir P. Beškoski, PhD, full professor from the UBFC completed his PhD in 2011 on the study of the activities of microorganisms and their application in bioremediation across laboratory, pilot, and industrial scales.

As an Invited Foreign Researcher supported by the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS), he spent over two years within the last decade at Kobe University, Japan, specializing in the biodegradation of persistent organic pollutants. He currently serves as the President of the Environmental Chemistry Division of the Serbian Chemical Society and as the National Representative in the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), Division VI: Chemistry and the Environment. Presently he is a Project leader of Horizon Europe project “PFAS_{Stwin}”, and project PhytoPFAS, funded by Science Fund of Serbia. In the past he was a project leader for several project funded by Innovation Fund of Serbia, several international projects funded by Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) and project VISION funded by multinational company Solvay Specialty Polymers Italy S.p.A. His scholarly output includes authoring 79 papers in peer-reviewed journals and four book chapters, with total citations 1466 and h-index=22 (Scopus database), (ORCID: 0000-0002-6372-4706). Dr. Beškoski research spans several facets of environmental biotechnology and microbial ecology, including the application of green chemistry principles in microbial processes, microbial activities and their applications in biogeotechnology, as well as metabolism of extremophiles in degradation of POPs chemicals, and applications of plants and microorganisms in bioremediation and sustainable agriculture.

INVITED LECTURE

PFAS FROM USEFUL CHEMICALS TO ENVIRONMENTAL HOT TOPIC - SOLVING THE (BIO)DEGRADATION PUZZLE

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Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) represent one of the most critical classes of emerging pollutants due to their extreme environmental persistence, bioaccumulative potential, and harmful effects on ecosystems and human health. Since the 1940s, PFAS have been used extensively across a wide range of industrial processes and consumer products, resulting in their global distribution in water sources, soil, air, and even human blood.

When PFAS are present in soil, they can leach into groundwater, posing risks of contaminating drinking water supplies and food chains. This pathway of exposure elevates the urgency for action. Therefore, there is a critical need to develop, optimize, and deploy targeted remediation technologies specifically designed for PFAS-contaminated soils, as conventional treatment methods often prove ineffective.

Phytoremediation is an environmentally friendly, *in situ* remediation approach that utilizes plants to absorb, stabilize, or degrade contaminants through their root systems. In addition to contaminant removal, phytoremediation helps prevent soil erosion, retain soil moisture, and enhance microbial activity and biodiversity, thereby minimizing secondary pollution such as dust dispersion or contaminant leaching. Several studies with varying levels of success have been conducted using different plant types, including herbaceous plants, wetland plant species, and woody plants, specifically focusing on the phytoremediation of soil and water contaminated with PFAS compounds.

Microbial bioremediation of PFAS is an emerging but still challenging field due to the extreme stability of carbon-fluorine bonds. Despite this, several studies have demonstrated that certain microbial strains possess the enzymatic potential to transform or degrade specific PFAS compounds under controlled conditions. The most frequently studied and relatively promising genera include *Acidimicrobium*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Gordonia*, as well as mixed microbial consortia, particularly within anaerobic or microaerophilic environments. These microbes are often associated with reductive defluorination processes, especially when it comes to shorter-chain perfluorinated carboxylic acids and sulfonates.

Recent advancements in metagenomics, transcriptomics, and protein engineering are accelerating the identification of PFAS-degrading enzymes (such as fluoroacetate dehalogenases), which may pave the way for synthetic biology approaches to develop more efficient strains.

Keywords: PFAS, phytoremediation, bioremediation

Acknowledgements: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme, Twinning Western Balkans, under grant agreement No. 101059534.

Snežana Maletić, PhD, is a Full Professor at the University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, and a recognized expert in environmental chemistry and protection.

With over 20 years of research experience, she has made significant contributions to soil quality, remediation technologies, and sustainable environmental solutions. Her work focuses on carbon-based materials like biochar and phytoremediation for soil and sediment remediation, as well as pollutant transport, bioavailability, and toxicity. She currently leads several major projects, including TwinSubDyn (Horizon Europe), ReNBES (Science Fund of Serbia), and a Serbia–China bilateral project on biochar and pesticide mobility.

She is also the Serbian pilot site leader for the Phy2Climate Horizon 2020 project. Prof. Maletić has managed over 30 international and national research projects and more than 80 industry collaborations. Since 2012, she has directed the ISO/IEC 17025-accredited Laboratory for Environmental Analysis. She has authored over 80 SCI-indexed papers, holds an h-index of 24, and has received multiple national awards for scientific excellence and international collaboration.

INVITED LECTURE

CARBON BASED AMENDMENTS ADVANCING SUSTAINABLE SOLUTIONS FOR CONTAMINATED ENVIRONMENTAL MATRICES

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Contaminated environmental matrices, including soils and sediments, present ongoing challenges to ecosystem integrity, human health, and sustainable land and water management. This research offers a detailed investigation into the potential of organic and carbon-based amendments, such as biochar, hydrochar, and compost-derived materials, to mitigate the risks posed by a broad spectrum of organic pollutants. Laboratory-based studies demonstrate that these amendments enhance contaminant retention by improving sorption capacity and modifying physicochemical properties of the matrices. By reducing pollutant mobility and bioavailability, amendments decrease the likelihood of contaminants leaching into groundwater or uptake by organisms. Additionally, the amendments contribute to the stimulation of microbial communities that can biodegrade certain classes of organic contaminants, thereby supporting natural attenuation processes. Comparative analyses of different amendment types reveal that material properties, including surface area, porosity, and chemical composition, critically influence sorption effectiveness and pollutant stabilization. Moreover, the interaction mechanisms between amendments and pollutants involve a combination of hydrophobic partitioning, π - π interactions, and surface complexation, which collectively govern the fate and transport of contaminants in environmental matrices. These findings underscore the versatility of organic amendments as tailored remediation tools that can be optimized according to site-specific contamination profiles and environmental conditions. Incorporating such amendments aligns with sustainable remediation principles and circular bioeconomy goals by utilizing waste-derived materials to restore ecosystem function and reduce environmental risk. Overall, this body of work highlights the promising role of carbon based amendments in enhancing the safety and quality of contaminated environmental matrices, offering a foundation for future applied research and the development of nature-based remediation strategies.

Keywords: environmental remediation, organic amendments, contaminant bioaccessibility, contaminant sorption, biodegradation

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ORAL PRESENTATIONS

ORAL PRESENTATION

INNOVATIONS IN CLIMATE-RESILIENT CROP BREEDING

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Climate change significantly impacts crop production, leading to reduced yields and increased risks of crop failures. Changes in temperature, rainfall and drought patterns, the frequency of extreme weather events as well as the emergence of new diseases and pests as a consequence of climate change negatively affect crop growth and development. Breeding has always had multiple objectives, however, climate change makes breeding objectives change more frequently than before. Tackling with such a complex problem requires using a comprehensive approach and introducing innovations. Within a project funded by the European Commission under the agreement No. 101059784 “Stepping up scientific excellence and innovation capacity for climate-resilient crop improvement and production” CROPINNO, a team of scientists from the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops are teaming up with respectable European research institutions and Universities to introduce novel techniques in climate-resilient crop breeding. One of the outcomes of CROPINNO is the establishment of the Center of Excellence for Innovations in Breeding of Climate-Resilient Crops – Climate Crops, which will continue the efforts in tackling with climate change to produce new climate-resilient crop varieties.

Keywords: climate change, climate-smart breeding, integrative agriculture, innovations

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ORAL PRESENTATION

SUNFLOWER UNDER STRESS: SUSTAINABLE BREEDING SOLUTIONS FOR DROUGHT ADAPTATION AND NUTRITION QUALITY IMPROVEMENT

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Climate change-induced drought is a critical challenge to global agriculture, particularly in semi-arid and arid regions. Sunflower, a moderately drought-tolerant oil crop, offers substantial potential for sustainable adaptation due to its deep root system and ecological flexibility. However, extended drought stress negatively impacts both yield and oil quality. Simultaneously, enhancing the nutritional value of sunflower oil remains a breeding priority to meet global dietary demands. Sustainable breeding solutions aim to develop sunflower genotypes that are both drought-resilient and nutritionally improved. This involves harnessing genetic diversity and employing advanced breeding techniques targeting traits such as drought escape, avoidance, and tolerance. Integrative “-omics” approaches—genomics, phenomics, transcriptomics, metabolomics, and epigenomics—enable deeper insight into complex traits and their interactions with environmental stress. High-throughput phenotyping, especially image-based methods, allows non-invasive and scalable analysis of plant traits, facilitating selection for root architecture, water use efficiency, and seed composition. These tools support the development of climate-smart, nutrient-enriched sunflower genotypes, aligning with global goals for environmentally sustainable agriculture and food security.

Keywords: sunflower, drought, omics-, oil quality, yield, root traits

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ORAL PRESENTATION

DEVELOPMENT OF BIORATIONAL METHODS FOR SEED PROTECTION DURING STORAGE AGAINST BIOTIC AND ABIOTIC STRESSORS

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Post-harvest period represents one of the most vulnerable periods in seed production and also a vital aspect of food security. However, less than 5% of the funding has been allocated for research on mitigation of post-harvest losses, indicating a state of neglect of this crucial part of agricultural production. During storage, seed pests are a major cause of huge postharvest losses (10-100%), but recently, due to climate change, inadequate storage conditions also pose a threat to preservation of seed quality and vitality. The **SafeSeed** project tends to answer this challenge by defining seed traits responsible for seed tolerance to biotic and abiotic stress as well as developing a seed protectant. We will use a holistic approach in developing new and improving existing pest management tools and optimizing preventive measures for seed storing with the ultimate aim of reducing postharvest losses. Accordingly, a large genetic pool of major field crops (maize, sunflower, legumes, cereals) will undergo extensive screening that will include: i) determination of main seed traits responsible for tolerance to seed insect pests using common and –omics phenotyping tools, ii) tolerance/preference assessment in insect biotests, iii) identification of protease inhibitors that will be used for formulating bioinsecticide and seed protectant, iv) bioinformatic tools for the integration of information from seed phenotyping and insect biotests that will result in the creation of pest tolerant ideotype. Defining seed traits responsible for tolerance towards a specific pest, and a new algorithm that will be developed, will enable further “smart” decisions in the breeding of pest-tolerant genotypes and in tolerance prediction. Furthermore, identified inhibitors will enable the development of seed protectant with an array of biotechnological applications. The main results and impacts of **SafeSeed** will be in the reduction of harvest losses in a sustainable manner with low or non-environmental footprint by the development of high-quality biorational and eco-friendly solutions for controlling stored product pests, thus increasing quality, seed availability and providing stable incomes for farmers, seed companies and industry. This project and its results are aligning with the goals of Environmental and Sustainable Research Solutions promoted by the TwINSol-CECs project.

Keywords: post-harvest losses, seed vitality, seed quality, biotic stressors, abiotic stressors, stored product pests, bioinsecticide, seed protectant

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ORAL PRESENTATION

BIOACTIVE ECDYSTEROID ANALOGUES: CINNAMATE ESTERS AND *TERT*-BUTYL OXIME ETHERS WITH ANTITRYPANOSOMAL PROPERTIES

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Chagas disease, recognised by the World Health Organisation as a neglected tropical disease, continues to pose a significant public health challenge, with an estimated annual incidence exceeding 170,000 new cases. While only a minority of infections develop into life-threatening complications, a markedly higher proportion of affected individuals suffer considerable reductions in disability-adjusted life years. The paucity of effective and safe therapeutic options underscores the pressing need for novel antitrypanosomal agents.

Ecdysteroids, a class of polyhydroxylated steroidal compounds featuring a characteristic 7-en-6-one configuration in the B-ring, have been widely studied for their anabolic, adaptogenic, and neuroprotective properties in mammals—without eliciting hormonal disturbances. In contrast, they function as key hormonal regulators of moulting in arthropods. Of particular interest, ecdysone has been implicated in modulating the life cycle of *Trypanosoma cruzi* by promoting parasite differentiation within the midgut of *Rhodnius prolixus*, a principal vector of the disease.

In the present study, a library of fifty-two ecdysteroid compounds' trypanocidal activity was screened against *Trypanosoma cruzi*. The results highlighted a promising correlation between antiparasitic efficacy and the presence of cinnamate ester and *tert*-butyl oxime ether functionalities. Based on these preliminary outcomes, a series of novel semi-synthetic derivatives incorporating both structural motifs was designed and prepared. The most effective trypanocidal activity was observed within the six newly obtained compounds, two cinnamate monoesters in the A ring of stachysterone B—each featuring a *tert*-butyl oxime ether moiety at the B ring—demonstrated. The lead compound underwent further evaluation through IC₅₀ determination using MTT and XTT assays, revealing a more than 6.5-fold higher selectivity towards *T. cruzi* epimastigotes relative to mammalian host cell cytotoxicity. Furthermore, flow cytometry-based quantification of parasite egress from infected cells confirmed its potent activity, yielding an IC₅₀ value of 2.7 µM.

Keywords: ecdysteroids, semi-synthesis, *Trypanosoma cruzi*

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ORAL PRESENTATION

PROTOFLAVONOIDS: EXPLORING THE NON-TUMOR-RELATED BIOACTIVITIES OF A RARE GROUP OF NATURAL PRODUCTS

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Protoflavonoids represent a rare, natural subgroup of flavonoids characterized by a non-aromatic B-ring and a hydroxyl moiety at C-1'. The B-ring of protoflavonoids is commonly a symmetric *p*-quinone dienone, a structural feature that provides cytotoxic properties to these compounds. While this cytotoxicity underlies the antitumor potential of protoflavones, it also hampers the thorough investigation of their non-cancer-related bioactivities. In recent years, our group has developed semi-synthetic approaches aimed at reducing the cytotoxicity of protoflavonoids and enhancing their non-cancer-related biological effects by structurally modifying the B-ring.

In our current work, we set out to semi-synthesize a structurally diverse compound library using protoapigenone and its 1'-O-alkylated derivatives as starting materials. The primary target of our synthetic work was the 4'-oxo group of compounds, which we successfully substituted with various nitrogen-containing functionalities, such as oxime ethers and hydrazones. The resulting products were purified by chromatographic techniques, including flash chromatography and reversed-phase HPLC. Structural elucidation of the compounds was performed using high-resolution mass spectrometry and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy. The semi-synthesized compounds were then tested *in vitro* for xanthine oxidase inhibitory activity and other biological effects.

To date, we have identified three different flavone- or protoflavone-type compounds capable of inhibiting xanthine oxidase at nanomolar concentrations. Among these, the most potent is a flavonoid diazene derivative, exhibiting an IC₅₀ value of 66 nM. This compound showed significantly higher selectivity, approximately 615-fold, in its antioxidant activity compared to its cytotoxic effect. Furthermore, the synthetically prepared compounds demonstrated a range of additional bioactivities with varying degrees of potency.

Keywords: protoflavonoids, protoapigenone, semi-synthesis, xanthine-oxidase

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ORAL PRESENTATION

INNOVATIVE *BACILLUS*-BASED TECHNOLOGY FOR PLANT GROWTH PROMOTION AND YIELD ENHANCEMENT IN SWEET POTATO FARMING

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The primary aim of the present work was to identify bacterial isolates with yield-enhancing potential for application as biofertilizers in sweet potato farming. Therefore, endophytic and rhizospheric strains were isolated from sweet potato plantations in Hungary to identify bacterial isolates with plant growth-promoting and antifungal potential. In total, seven *Bacillus licheniformis* strains were identified and subjected to detailed ecophysiological tests. Experiments have been conducted to investigate the tolerance of selected strains to different limiting factors such as pH, temperature, water activity, drought and pesticides which affect survivability in various agricultural environments. The majority of tested *B. licheniformis* strains exhibited plant growth-promoting potential (e.g., production of indole-3-acetic acid up to 40.42 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, production of ammonia up to 0.87 mg mL^{-1} , phosphorus solubilising activity, siderophore production), with two strains (SZMC 27713 and SZMC 27715) demonstrating inhibitory activity (ranging between 7 and 38%) against plant pathogenic fungi occurring in sweet potato cultivation. Furthermore, strain SZMC 27715 induced accelerated germination and a significantly higher germination rate in tomato seeds compared to the control. In addition, it was observed that the SZMC 27715 isolate significantly increased the total root length and the number of developing lateral roots of *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Col-0) seedlings. In a field trial, it was found that strain SZMC 27715 had a prominent yield enhancing effect in sweet potato, where a significant yield per plant increase was observed in all treatments (1.13 kg, 1.09 kg and 1.40 kg) in comparison to the untreated control plants (0.92 kg). The highest yield per plant was observed when the cuttings were soaked combined with two additional foliar treatments. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study of the successful application of the *B. licheniformis* strain as a biofertilizer for yield enhancement in the cultivation of sweet potato. Based on our results, strain SZMC 27715 has potential for application as a biofertilizer in sweet potato cultivation either as a standalone option or in a microbial consortium. Currently, we are elaborating a novel formulation of the *Bacillus*-based foliar treatment, supported by advanced analytical methods.

Keywords: *Bacillus licheniformis*, sweet potato, endophytic, plant growth-promoting bacteria (PGPB), biofertilizer

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ORAL PRESENTATION

THE POTENTIAL OF DIGESTATE- AND *Bacillus*-BASED CIRCULAR SOIL AMENDMENT TO ENHANCE EARLY TOMATO DEVELOPMENT

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Biogas is produced through anaerobic digestion of various organic waste materials, including agricultural residues, livestock manure, municipal sewage sludge, green waste, and food waste. This process is driven by the metabolic activity of anaerobic and methanogenic bacteria, which decompose organic matter under oxygen-free conditions. The main by-product of biogas production is digestate, which contains significant residual amounts of N, P, K, and Ca, with a potential to serve not only as a direct biofertilizer but also as a cultivation medium for beneficial microorganisms. Among them, *Bacillus* spp. are well known for their plant growth-promoting (PGP) properties. In this study, biogas digestate derived from meat industry effluents was used as a base medium for the cultivation of *Bacillus* sp. BioSol021, previously isolated from the rhizosphere of *Phaseolus vulgaris* and identified as *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, to obtain a circular soil amendment. The cultivation medium was prepared by diluting digestate with water at a 1:9 (v/v) ratio and by sterilization via autoclaving to eliminate the native digestate microflora. The medium was inoculated with 10% (v/v) of the bacterial culture, and cultivation was conducted on a laboratory shaker at 28 °C for 96 hours under spontaneous aeration. The PGP effect of the resulting cultivation broth was evaluated by treating tomato seeds (*Solanum lycopersicum*) and monitoring early growth parameters (root and shoot lengths, fresh and dry mass of tomato seedlings) after 7 days of incubation at room temperature. The seeds treated with tap water served as the control. The digestate-based medium proved suitable for supporting bacterial growth, reaching a final viable cell number of 9 log CFU/mL after 96 hours of cultivation. Tomato seed germination in the treatment group reached 80%, compared to 60% in the control group. The mean root and shoot lengths of the treated seedlings were 8.00 ± 6.84 mm and 3.30 ± 2.87 mm, respectively, while in the control group they were 6.90 ± 4.21 mm and 2.90 ± 1.23 mm. The mean fresh mass of treated and untreated seedlings was 10.30 ± 2.86 mg and 7.92 ± 3.60 mg, respectively, while dry mass was 6.12 ± 0.88 mg and 4.97 ± 1.99 mg. These results suggest that *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, when cultivated using biogas digestate, not only enhances seed germination but also significantly improves early seedling development of tomato plants. The observed increases in root and shoot length, as well as fresh and dry biomass, indicate improved nutrient uptake and the overall plant vigor. Such enhancements in biomass accumulation at early growth stages may contribute to more resilient plants with better survival potential and productivity under field conditions. These findings support the potential application of digestate-based *Bacillus* formulations as effective dual-function soil amendments that combine nutrient supply with microbial stimulation of plant growth. Future research should aim to optimize cultivation and formulation conditions, investigate the mechanisms underlying PGP, and evaluate the efficacy and stability of digestate-based *Bacillus* formulations through *in vivo* experiments and field-scale applications.

Keywords: biogas digestate, Bacillus amiloliquefaciens, plant growth promotion, tomato seed germination, circular economy

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ORAL PRESENTATION

PASSIVE BUT PROMISING: PASSIVE SAMPLING OF PER- AND POLYFLUOROALKYL ACIDS (PFAAS) IN WASTEWATER

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Per- and polyfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) are a subgroup of the highly persistent per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), which frequently enter the aquatic environment via wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). As they are highly toxic to the environment and human health, monitoring regulations have been introduced under the EU Urban Wastewater Directive. Starting 2027, PFAS must be monitored in the inflows and outflows of wastewater treatment plants $\geq 10,000$ PE. To keep these levels to a minimum, identifying the source can be beneficial. By using passive monitoring with polar organic chemical integrative samplers (POCIS), PFAA can be detected in low concentrations. In wastewater (WW), various matrix parameters can influence the sorption on POCIS and compromise the quantification accuracy. The aim of our research was to identify a suitable POCIS sorbent for WW and evaluate the parameter effects. The following five ion exchange sorbents were selected for POCIS: Fuelcellstore FUMASEP FAD-PET-75 (FAD) (FuelCellStore, USA), AG MP-1M AEX Resin (AEX) (Bio-Rad, USA), AG 501-X8(D) Mixed Bed Resin (MIX) (Bio-Rad, USA), Oasis WAX (WAX) (Waters, USA), and Oasis HLB (HLB) (Waters, USA). Batch tests were carried out with these sorbents using PFAA-spiked synthetic WW and deionized (DI) water. We found that HLB performed well for long-chain PFAAs (C8-C11) but less well for short-chain (C5-C7), compared to WAX, which performed consistently well for all chain lengths (C5-C11). The sorption performance in the WW was significantly less efficient than in DI, which can be attributed to the complex matrix. For further investigation of the WW parameters, WAX was selected. Batch tests with pH (5, 8, 12), NaCl (7, 50, 1000 mg/L), humic substances (0, 10, 1000 mg/L COD) and organic substances (0, 50, 100 % true WW) are ongoing. In the standard range (6-9), the pH value has little influence on the speciation of PFAS; however, anion exchangers show a lower sorption capacity at higher pH values. Salinity can influence the sorption of PFAS by salting out, which increases sorption. High salinity concentrations, humic substances and organic substances can act as competing ions and compounds due to their polarity and interfere with the sorption. This experiment allows us to determine the optimum conditions for PFAA sorption in WW. Deviations from these conditions can thus be considered for *in-situ* sampling campaigns and extend the applicability of passive samplers to complex water matrices.

Keywords: PFAS, passive sampling, wastewater monitoring, water pollution

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ORAL PRESENTATION

MITIGATING TRANSPORT OF IONIZABLE ORGANIC POLLUTANTS IN ALLUVIAL SOILS USING BIOCHAR

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The transport and retention of organic pollutants in alluvial soils depend on various site-specific factors, including the filter medium properties, environmental conditions, and chemical nature of the pollutants. The transport behavior of four chlorophenols (4-chlorophenol, 2,4-dichlorophenol, 2,4,6-trichlorophenol, and pentachlorophenol) was studied in highly permeable sandy layers of Danube alluvial soil using column experiments under saturated conditions. In unamended soils, complete breakthrough of all compounds occurred within 10 hours, indicating poor retention capacity. Only pentachlorophenol exhibited moderate retardation, while the more polar compounds behaved similarly to the non-sorbing tracer. A strong correlation between retardation coefficients (R_d) and the compounds' acid dissociation constants (pK_a) was observed in these layers.

To improve retention, 0.5% biochar was added to the same soil layers. This significantly prolonged the transport of chlorophenols, with breakthrough occurring after 72-400 hours. The modeled R_d values increased notably: 2,4,6-TCP (42-78), PCP (74-108), 2,4-DCP (82-115), and 4-CP (102-155), compared to those obtained for unamended soils. The enhanced retention is attributed to the biochar's large surface area, aromatic structure, and oxygen-containing functional groups, which facilitate hydrophobic, π - π , and electrostatic interactions. The biochar's high point of zero charge (10.8) allows its surface to be positively charged under natural aquifer pH, favoring attraction of ionized chlorophenols.

While aquifer materials can retain many contaminants, the results of this study highlight the risk of pollutant breakthrough and groundwater contamination, particularly for more polar compounds, underscoring the potential of biochar-amended filtration zones to mitigate such risks.

Keywords: ionizable organic pollutants, alluvial soil, biochar

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ORAL PRESENTATION

BIOMONITORING OF NON-OCCUPATIONAL ARSENIC EXPOSURE AMONG ADVANCED LUNG CANCER PATIENTS IN VOJVODINA

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Arsenic is wide spread global contaminant and Group 1 IARC carcinogen threatening human health due to intake through air, food and water. The newest findings indicate that exposure to low and moderate arsenic levels (<150 µg/L) are associated with elevated risk of developing or dying from lung cancer.

In this study a total of 190 lung IIIB/IV stage cancer patients of both genders (105 males and 85 females) from the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia were enrolled, 61 of whom were diagnosed with small-cell lung cancer, while 129 were diagnosed with non-small cell lung cancer (67 with lung adenocarcinoma and 62 with squamous cell lung cancer). Their first morning, urine sample was collected within 24h of hospitalization. Each sample was prepared using microwave digestion and tested for arsenic using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry analysis.

In 87.89% (167/190) samples arsenic was measured above the limit of quantification (LOQ) with no differences between genders as arsenic was above LOQ in 90.48% (95/105) samples of male patients and in 84.71% (72/85) samples of female patients. There were no statistical differences in the urinary arsenic values between genders ($p=0.323$) as the mean concentrations and standard deviations were 23.45 ± 39.89 µg/L for males vs. 18.05 ± 26.65 µg/L for female participants. The urinary arsenic concentrations were highest among patients with squamous cell lung cancer with 29.62 ± 48.04 µg/L and higher when compared to the levels measured among patients with small-cell lung cancer (15.80 ± 28.37 , $p=0.085$) and compared to those with lung adenocarcinoma (17.21 ± 20.70 , $p=0.066$), respectively with borderline significance in both cases. Since none of the participants was occupationally exposed to arsenic, environmental sources were observed as the main pathway of exposure.

Water remains one of the principal sources of exposure to arsenic. In the region of Vojvodina ground waters are endangered by arsenic with up to 750 µg/L while the concentration of arsenic in the drinking water is usually between 10 and 100 µg/L. Besides, the arsenic daily intake in Vojvodina in 2000 through food was estimated to be 60.9 ± 22.3 µg/day. There is an urgent need for regulatory measures to protect the general population from the cancer risks associated with arsenic exposure.

Keywords: arsenic, lung cancer, environmental pollution

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ORAL PRESENTATION

COMPARATIVE LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF SEWAGE SLUDGE MANAGEMENT OPTIONS IN SERBIA

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Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is crucial for evaluating sewage sludge management options, as it provides a comprehensive understanding of their environmental impacts and helps identify strategies with the lowest environmental burdens and highest resource efficiency. This study conducts a comparative LCA of three potential sewage sludge management strategies in Serbia: S0 – disposal in unsanitary landfills, S1 – application to agricultural land with nutrient recovery, and S2 – incineration with energy recovery. The assessment covers the full treatment chain, from the collection of anaerobically digested sewage sludge at a wastewater treatment plant with a projected capacity of 150,000 PE to its final disposal or reuse. The analysis reveals that S0 generally exhibits the highest environmental burdens, primarily due to uncontrolled methane emissions, leachate generation, and the absence of resource recovery. In contrast, the comparative outcomes for S1 and S2 are more complex. Land application (S1) offers benefits in resource conservation by offsetting mineral fertilizer use but poses risks of heavy metal accumulation and nutrient runoff, potentially leading to soil and water contamination. Incineration (S2) reduces sludge volume and enables energy recovery, but it is associated with higher air pollutant emissions and challenges related to ash management. The preference between S1 and S2 strongly depends on the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method used. Different LCIA methods—such as ReCiPe, USEtox, and Impact World+—prioritize and quantify environmental impacts differently due to variations in impact category coverage, the range of environmental flows considered, characterization models, regionalization, and weighting factors. These methodological differences often lead to divergent impact assessments and scenario rankings. Therefore, while S0 is generally the least favorable option across most impact categories, the optimal choice between S1 and S2 is contingent upon the specific environmental priorities and the LCIA method employed.

Keywords: sewage sludge management, life cycle assessment, nutrient recovery, waste-to-energy

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ORAL PRESENTATION

UV/CHLORINE PROCESS FOR DEGRADATION OF IBUPROFEN AND TRIMETHOPRIM IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

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Pharmaceutical active ingredients are released into municipal wastewater due to their daily use and limited utilization in the human body. However, conventional water treatment processes are not suitable for completely removing all active pharmaceutical ingredients - the persistent, non-biodegradable components make the introduction of quaternary, additional water treatment processes necessary. One group of these additional processes is the Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP), which are based on radical generation.

This study investigated the UV/chlorine process to eliminate ibuprofen (IBU), a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug, and trimethoprim (TRIM) antibiotic. Both persistent pollutants are commonly detected in surface water, groundwater, and even drinking water sources. Chlorination (Cl_2 or HOCl) is one of the most often used disinfection methods in water treatment. UV photolysis of chlorine-containing disinfectant produces various radicals, such as hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) and various Cl-containing reactive species (e.g. $\text{Cl}\bullet$, $\text{ClO}\bullet$). The reactions of radicals contribute to the decomposition of organic contaminants. Thus, disinfection and removal of trace contaminants occur in one step. Due to the absorption spectrum of HOCl and OCl^- , widely used low-pressure mercury vapor lamps can be replaced by suitable UV-C LED light sources.

In this work, the photolysis of Freely Available Chlorine (FAC: HOCl/OCl^- ($\text{pK}_a = 7.54$)) and the elimination of two selected pharmaceuticals using the UV/FAC process was studied, using LED light sources emits at 265 nm and 275 nm. The effect of pH (6–11), photon fluxes ($0.80\text{--}3.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol}_{\text{photon}} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ L}^{-1}$), and FAC concentration (0 – 1.0 mM) were studied. Direct reaction with HOCl (without irradiation) caused a transformation of TRIM at $\text{pH} < 9$, while IBU did not react with FAC. At the same time, the contribution of direct photolysis was only significant in the case of IBU. Increasing the FAC concentration in the UV/FAC process enhanced the conversion rate in all cases. The HOCl/OCl^- ratio determines the radical set. The formation and relative contribution of various radicals to the transformation of target compounds were investigated using radical scavengers and nitrobenzene as a probe compound. With increasing pH, the contribution of HOCl and $\bullet\text{OH}$ -initiated reactions to overall transformation decreased, whereas the role of chlorine-containing reactive species became dominant. At pH 6, the steady-state concentration of $\bullet\text{OH}$ was 20 times higher than at pH 11.

The matrix components can significantly reduce the effectiveness of the methods. The extent of this must be known for practical use. Biologically treated domestic wastewater was used as a matrix. A slightly enhanced transformation rate for TRIM was observed, highlighting the significant role of chlorine-containing radicals.

This work contributes to studying AOPs for removing pharmaceuticals and supports optimizing UV/chlorine systems for practical applications.

Keywords: LED, pharmaceuticals, antibiotics, advanced oxidation processes, UV/chlorine, HOCl/OCl⁻

ORAL PRESENTATION

FROM CAPTURE TO DESTRUCTION: A TWO-STEP CONCEPT FOR PFOA REMEDIATION IN AQUEOUS SYSTEMS

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Due to its exceptional chemical stability and resistance to degradation, perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) represents one of the most challenging pollutants in aquatic environments. This study proposes an integrated remediation concept combining adsorption, desorption, and photocatalytic degradation as a potentially efficient and scalable solution for PFOA removal from wastewater. In the first phase, various adsorbents—including granular and powdered activated carbon, as well as ion exchange resins—were employed to capture PFOA from diluted aqueous matrices. Among them, powdered activated carbon K/B and the strongly basic resin Amberlite IRA 402 demonstrated the highest sorption capacities.

To optimize the subsequent degradation process, the adsorbed PFOA was desorbed, resulting in a concentrated eluate. This concentration step significantly enhances the feasibility and efficiency of advanced treatment methods. The desorbed solution was then subjected to photocatalytic degradation using titanium dioxide coatings doped with reduced graphene oxide (rGO), synthesized by plasma electrolytic oxidation. The incorporation of rGO enhanced the photocatalytic performance by narrowing the band gap, increasing oxygen vacancies, and reducing charge carrier recombination. The degradation proceeded via a stepwise shortening of the PFOA molecule, generating perfluoroheptanoic, perfluorohexanoic, and perfluoropentanoic acids, along with the release of fluoride ions. Treated samples exhibited reduced toxicity to the bioluminescent bacterium *Aliivibrio fischeri*.

This two-step approach enables efficient capture and targeted degradation of persistent pollutants, offering a controlled and resource-efficient pathway toward sustainable wastewater treatment technologies.

Keywords: PFOA remediation, adsorption–desorption, photocatalytic degradation, wastewater treatment

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ORAL PRESENTATION

THE INVESTIGATION OF THE RADICAL SET IN PERSULFATE IONS ASSISTED HETEROGENEOUS PHOTOCATALYSIS

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Removal of non-biodegradable and/or biologically active trace pollutants is an urgent problem in wastewater treatment. To this, the use of advanced oxidation processes, including heterogeneous photocatalysis, might offer a solution. In this process, on the surface of a photoexcited semiconductor (photocatalyst), the photogenerated charge carriers (electrons and holes) can react with various adsorbed substances, resulting in the formation of reactive radicals, that can initiate the transformation of organic pollutants. The efficiency of this process can be increased by oxidizing agents to the system, for example, persulfate ions (peroxymonosulfate ion (HSO_5^- , PMS) or peroxydisulfate ion ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, PDS)). In this work, the effect of PMS and PDS was investigated in the case of ZnO photocatalyst. The suspensions were irradiated by LEDs emitting 367 nm photons. The effect of PS concentration, dissolved O_2 , and radical scavengers was studied.

As an excellent electron acceptor, PS enhances the separation of photogenerated charge carriers and the rate of hole-mediated oxidation processes, including $\cdot\text{OH}$ formation. Moreover, electron capture by PS results in sulfate radical ion ($\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$) having similar reactivity as hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$). Besides, singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) formation is also possible and contributes to the transformation, especially in the case of PMS. Due to the various processes, a complex radical set forms in the case of PS-assisted heterogeneous photocatalysis.

Organic substances (trimethoprim, nitrobenzene, and hydroquinone) were selected as target compounds; selection was based on their reactivity toward various reactive species, such as hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$), sulfate radical ion ($\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$) and singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$). Although nitrobenzene reacts primarily with $\cdot\text{OH}$, the addition of PDS significantly enhanced its transformation rate. The results showed that PS's effect is primarily attributed to promoting $\cdot\text{OH}$ formation and, to a lesser extent, to the formation and reactions of $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$. However, hydroquinone reacts primarily with $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ and $^1\text{O}_2$, while $\cdot\text{OH}$ had little to no role when PS were introduced to the suspension, further proving the complex nature of heterogeneous photocatalytic processes.

The role of emerging H_2O_2 and the transformation of the oxidants (PMS and PDS) were also investigated, giving a deeper understanding of the complex interactions between the main chemical species. In PS-free suspension, H_2O_2 accumulation can be observed during the transformation of organic substances. Addition of PDS and PMS accelerated the transformation of H_2O_2 . Most probably, H_2O_2 served as an excellent $\cdot\text{OH}$ and $^1\text{O}_2$ source. The effect of radical scavengers (t-butanol, methanol, and furfuryl alcohol) confirmed that PS addition greatly enhanced the $\cdot\text{OH}$ formation rate, even in O_2 -free suspension and cannot be interpreted only in terms of the enhanced charge separation efficiency. However, the radical scavengers proved to be quite interfering, as their presence could alter both the H_2O_2 accumulation rate and slightly accelerate the PS transformation rate. This means that despite radical scavenger experiments are widely used in literature, their effect must be interpreted carefully.

Keywords: persulfate ions, heterogeneous photocatalysis, zinc oxide, trimethoprim

ORAL PRESENTATION

INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFICIENCY OF MELAMINE-MODIFIED BIOCHAR-BASED PHOTOCATALYSTS IN PERSULFATE-BASED AOPS FOR TRIMETHOPRIM DEGRADATION

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Refractory organic contaminants (ROCs) like antibiotics have been increasingly detected in wastewater. Persulfate-based advanced oxidation processes (PS-AOPs) are promising for eliminating ROCs such as trimethoprim. Recent studies indicate that biochar and its composite can effectively enhance adsorption and catalytic capabilities in PS-AOPs. This study investigates the production of grass-pellet-based biochar (GPBC) at various pyrolysis temperatures (400°C to 800°C) and its modification with melamine for the activation of peroxymonosulfate (PMS) to degrade TMP.

Grass-pellet biochar was produced at different temperatures and most effective biochar (700°C) was selected for composite preparation with melamine in varying ratios (GPBC: M from 1:0.025 to 1:2). Addition of melamine can affect the activity of biochar in two different ways: N-doped biochar formation and strong interaction between biochar and g-C₃N₄ dots (formed from melamine via pyrolysis), both able to promote the electron transfer. Two synthesis methods were employed: (1) Mixing melamine with raw grass-pellet (GP) material followed by pyrolysis at 700°C. (2) Combining pre-prepared GPBC at 700°C with melamine and reheating at 550°C in N₂ atmosphere. The performance of pristine GPBC and its composites (GPBC-M) in activating PMS and degrading TMP was evaluated.

For GPBC, an enhanced degradation efficiency with decreased adsorption capacity was observed as pyrolysis temperature increased from 400°C to 700 °C, emphasizing the significant influence of pyrolysis temperature on biochar's catalytic properties. The pristine GPBC prepared at 700°C showed low TMP adsorption and less than 20% degradation (96%) of 5×10⁻⁵ M trimethoprim in 60 min with 2 mM PMS. The GPBC₇₀₀-M composite proved to have better efficiency; the transformation rate increased with the weight of added melamine. The catalysts prepared from a 1:2 GP: melamine weight ratio showed the best activity; the complete removal of trimethoprim was reached within 40 min. Conversely, composites synthesized using the second method exhibited lower efficiency (no more than 44% degradation).

Grass-pellet biochar effectively activates PMS for TMP degradation, and its catalytic performance can be significantly improved when combined with melamine, particularly when integrated with raw materials. This study highlights the importance of pyrolysis temperature on adsorption and catalytic properties and the strategic preparation of composite materials. Future research will focus on the examination of composite structure, morphology, catalytic mechanisms, and the impact of various ions using real wastewater samples.

Keywords: biochar, trimethoprim, melamine, degradation, composite synthesis, PS-AOP

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

POSTER PRESENTATION

PHENOL REMOVAL FROM WATER USING FIR BIOWASTE-DERIVED PYROCHAR

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Throughout the world, various industrial processes, such as petroleum refineries, petrochemical industries, coke ovens, coal conversion, etc., discharge wastewater containing a wide spectrum of organic compounds, including phenol. The discharge of phenol-containing wastewaters into waterways seriously disrupts life in aquatic ecosystems. In order to protect the environment, it is necessary to choose the appropriate treatment for purifying wastewater before its release into the environment. Adsorption is considered one of the most optimal methods for removing phenol, which is easy to perform, and various materials can be used as adsorbents. Adsorbents that have proven to be very effective in removing phenols from water are biochars, which are environmentally friendly and inexpensive carbon materials. Biochar is obtained by pyrolysis of biomass and can be prepared from various raw materials such as wood waste, agricultural waste, etc. The possibility of obtaining biochar from various feedstocks, as well as from waste plant material, provides an opportunity for new research that would facilitate the use of waste biomaterial to obtain efficient adsorbents for water treatment. In this study, the efficiency of waste wood-derived pyrochar as an adsorbent for phenol removal from water was investigated. The biochar was produced from waste fir sawdust by pyrolysis at a temperature of 700 °C for a duration of 1 h, and used as an adsorbent. Phenol solution in deionized water in a concentration of 1 mM without pH correction (pH 5) was used as a wastewater model. Water treatment was using 8 g/L of biochar at 25 °C for 24 hours. The use of fir-derived biochar achieves an efficiency of 90% for phenol removal after 5 minutes of water treatment. The efficiency did not change significantly with increasing reaction time. The results obtained in this analysis suggest that the selected biochar represents a promising adsorbent for phenol removal from water by the adsorption process.

Keywords: biochar, fir sawdust, water treatment, adsorption, phenol removal

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POSTER PRESENTATION

SUSTAINABLE PHYTOREMEDIATION AND BIOFUEL PRODUCTION USING BRASSICA NAPUS ON MULTI-CONTAMINATED SEDIMENTS

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Phytoremediation represents an eco-friendly solution for restoring contaminated lands while enabling sustainable biofuel production. This study, conducted within the H2020 Phy2Climate project led by the Faculty of Technology, University of Novi Sad, explores the potential of Brassica napus for phytoextraction of multi-element contaminated dredged sediment. Field trials were conducted in 2022 and 2023 at a dredged sediment landfill along the Begej Canal, near the Serbian-Romanian border, covering a total area of approximately 2000 m². Given the heterogeneity of the deposited sediment, the landfill was divided into 10 subplots, each analyzed individually. The winter variety of Brassica napus 'Zlatna' was sown at a density of 50 seeds/m² in September 2022 and harvested at full maturity in July 2023. The estimated seed yield reached 380 kg (1.9 t/ha), with an additional 1600 kg of dry biomass collected. Analysis of metal concentrations in the harvested biomass, along with bioaccumulation and transfer factors, indicated that Brassica napus holds significant potential for the remediation of multi-contaminated sediments. Furthermore, the harvested biomass presents an opportunity for sustainable biofuel production, aligning with the goals of Environmental and Sustainable Research Solutions promoted by the TwINSol-CECs project.

Keywords: phytoremediation, biofuel production, brassica napus, multi-contaminated sediments, environmental sustainability

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POSTER PRESENTATION

EVALUATION OF NANOFILTRATION MEMBRANE MATERIAL IMPACT ON THE REMOVAL OF PHARMACEUTICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS

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Pharmaceutically active compounds are recurrently detected in aquatic environment and represent a major concern due to inefficient removal by often used wastewater treatment processes. Hence, advanced treatments, such as nanofiltration, are essential for their efficient removal from water sources. The aim of this study was to evaluate the impact of different membrane material on removal of pharmaceutically active compounds by three nanofiltration membranes with MWCO 200 Da. Acetaminophen, carbamazepine and salbutamol were selected as representatives of pharmaceutically active compounds, whereas selected membrane materials were polyamide, cellulose acetate and polypiperazine. METCell dead-end equipment was used to evaluate nanofiltration membrane performance. The highest rejection values for all compounds were observed when using polyamide membrane (70.96% - 98.14%), whereas the lowest rejection values were observed when using cellulose acetate membrane (49.10% - 63.46%). Rejection values for three pharmaceutically active compounds ranged from 57.60% to 78.34% when polypiperazine membrane was used. Rejection values of salbutamol and carbamazepine were higher compared to acetaminophen by all membranes. Molecular masses of acetaminophen, carbamazepine and salbutamol are 151.1 Da, 236.3 Da and 239.3 Da, respectively. Lower molecular mass of acetaminophen caused lower rejection values obtained by using nanofiltration membranes. Differences between rejection values of carbamazepine and salbutamol (with similar molecular masses), indicated possible influence of electrostatic interactions and hydrophobic interactions on rejection. Based on the obtained results, the most efficient membrane material for removal of selected compounds was polyamide, followed by polypiperazine, whereas cellulose acetate membrane had the lowest performance.

Keywords: water treatment, nanofiltration, pharmaceutically active compounds

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POSTER PRESENTATION

METHYLENE BLUE REMOVAL FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION USING HYDROCHARS DERIVED FROM PEACH AND APRICOT POMACE

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Water pollution caused by synthetic dyes such as methylene blue (MB) has become a growing environmental concern due to their widespread application in industries such as textile, paper, plastic, and cosmetics. The extensive use of MB is accompanied by serious environmental and health concerns in aqueous environments, primarily due to its high solubility, resistance to biodegradation, and toxicity to aquatic organisms and humans. Among various treatment methods, adsorption has gained considerable attention for MB removal owing to its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, high efficiency, and environmental compatibility. In this context, hydrochars have emerged as effective adsorbents. This study investigates the adsorption potential of hydrochars derived from peach and apricot pomace, obtained via hydrothermal carbonization under controlled conditions (260 °C, 50 bar, solid-to-liquid ratio 1:10 w/w, 30 min reaction time). The batch adsorption experiments were performed at the ambient temperature and pressure, with a stirring rate of 400 rpm, an initial concentration of MB of 10 mg/L, and the adsorbent dose of 0.4 g/L. The effect of contact time on the removal efficiency of MB was also investigated. The results demonstrated a significant effect of contact time on the adsorption performance, with removal efficiency increasing for both hydrochars as contact time increased. The hydrochar derived from peach pomace exhibited the highest performance, achieving removal efficiency of 85.15% after 2 h. A comparable removal efficiency of 83.90% was obtained for apricot pomace-derived hydrochar after 2.5 h. The corresponding adsorption capacities were 21.3 mg/g and 20.9 mg/g, respectively. These findings highlight the potential of peach and apricot pomace-derived hydrochars as effective, sustainable adsorbents for MB removal from aqueous systems.

Keywords: adsorption, apricot and peach pomace, hydrochar, methylene blue

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POSTER PRESENTATION

SOLVENT-ASSISTED METHANOLYSIS OF WASTE POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE

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Plastics have become indispensable materials in nearly all industrial sectors and daily life, primarily due to their low price, ease of production, and high resistance to water, air, and various chemicals. However, their extensive use led to significant environmental challenges, particularly concerning end-of-life management and persistent pollution. Among the most promising strategies for addressing these issues is the development of efficient recycling technologies, such as chemical depolymerization, which facilitate the reuse of plastic materials. In this study, waste bottles made of polyethylene terephthalate (PET), the most used polymer in plastic packaging, were subjected to KOH catalyzed methanolysis in the presence of different cosolvents to evaluate their influence on depolymerization efficiency. The reaction was performed in a stirred batch reactor under the following reaction conditions: temperature 70 °C, methanol-to-PET molar ratio 50:1, cosolvent-to-PET molar ratio 50:1, and KOH-to-PET molar ratio 0.5:1. The tested cosolvents included dichloromethane, tetrahydrofuran, acetonitrile, and chloroform. The results revealed a clear influence of cosolvent type on PET conversion. The highest PET conversion (97%) was achieved using tetrahydrofuran after 30 min, followed closely by dichloromethane (96%). In contrast, acetonitrile resulted in a significantly lower conversion of 52%, while no depolymerization observed in the presence of chloroform, even after 6 h of reaction. These findings demonstrate that tetrahydrofuran and dichloromethane, are highly effective cosolvents for catalytic methanolysis of waste PET, offering a viable approach for the chemical recycling of waste PET.

Keywords: polyethylene terephthalate, recycling, methanolysis

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POSTER PRESENTATION

KINETICS OF QUICKLIME-CATALYZED METHANOLYSIS OF HEMP SEED OIL

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Hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L) is classified as an industrial crop with versatile applications. Its seeds are a source of non-edible oil, containing approximately 25%-35% oil by weight, thus representing a valuable feedstock for biodiesel production. In this study, biodiesel was produced from hemp seed oil (HSO) via a two-step methanolysis process. The first step involved acid-catalyzed esterification of free fatty acids to reduce the acid value of the oil, followed by quicklime-catalyzed methanolysis of esterified HSO. This study aims to model the kinetics of methanolysis reaction, considering the importance of a reliable kinetic model for predicting reaction behavior on a larger scale and ensuring consistent biodiesel productivity. The quicklime-catalyzed methanolysis of esterified HSO was conducted under the batch conditions at catalyst amounts of 3, 5, and 7% (based on the HSO mass), methanol-to-HSO molar ratios of 6:1, 9:1 and 12:1, and a reaction temperature of 60 °C. The variation of fatty acid methyl esters over reaction time indicated two distinct reaction stages, an initial stage controlled by triacylglycerols (TAGs) mass transfer limitation, followed by chemically controlled reaction stage. A pseudo-first-order kinetic model was employed to describe the kinetics of the methanolysis and two kinetic parameters, volumetric TAG mass transfer coefficient and apparent reaction rate constant, were determined. The volumetric TAG mass transfer coefficient increased with increasing catalyst amount, whereas the apparent reaction rate constant was not influenced by the catalyst amount. Both parameters were found to be independent of the methanol amount. The validity of applied kinetic model was confirmed by low mean percent relative deviation (10.9%) between predicted and experimental data of TAG conversion degree. Based on the obtained results, the pseudo-first-order kinetic model can be recommended for predicting the TAG conversion degree during the HSO methanolysis under the investigated conditions.

Keywords: biodiesel, hemp seed oil, kinetics, quicklime

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POSTER PRESENTATION

DEVELOPMENT OF RENEWABLE POLYURETHANE BIOCOMPOSITES FOR WASTEWATER TREATMENT

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This study deals with development of renewable polyurethane composites for removal of toxic pollutants from water. The polyurethane composites were obtained by using various agro-industrial waste materials including waste cooking oil, *S. cerevisiae* waste biomass and wheat straw ash. Biobased polyols for polyurethane manufacture were obtained by esterification of waste cooking oil with diethylene glycol at 180°C. *S. cerevisiae* waste biomass was used as unmodified and modified, respectively. Modification of *S. cerevisiae* biomass was performed by an activation using K₂CO₃ and pyrolyzed at 700°C in tubular furnace and in an inert atmosphere. Wheat straw ash was used as a source of silica. The extraction of silicate solution from wheat straw ash was performed by the multi-step sequential extraction using 2,5 mol/L NaOH. Silica particles were generated from supersaturated sodium silicate solution. Biopolyols, *S. cerevisiae* biomass and silica particles were mixed together followed by addition of appropriate amount of methylene diphenyl diisocyanate for polyurethane synthesis. Porosity of composites were tuned with small aliquots of water. These composites have been explored for treating or elimination of several organic and inorganic pollutants from wastewater. In some instances the removal percentage of the contaminants was above 90%. The presented data reveals the efficiency of composite materials in wastewater treatment over the conventional singular materials.

Keywords: polyurethane, renewable materials, biocomposite, water treatment, activated carbon, silica

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POSTER PRESENTATION

PINEWOOD-BASED B-DOPED PYROCHAR WITH ENHANCED SURFACE AFFINITY FOR CATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN

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Chemicals are continuously released into the environment, resulting in a huge threat to aquatic ecosystems and human beings from so-called contaminants of emerging concern (CECs). Many of these compounds are detected in trace concentration in various water matrices, but are not the subject of routine monitoring or emission control. Traditional methods for wastewater treatment are not adequate enough to enable their efficient elimination. Persulfate-based advanced oxidation processes (PS-AOPs) have been recently recognized as a cutting-edge solution designed to avoid secondary contamination by oxidizing CECs to biodegradable or harmless substances, carbon-dioxide, and water. The addition of a metal-free heterogeneous catalyst into the system has been widely applied in order to empower high efficiency and easy operation of the process, as well as low energy consumption. The design of appropriate catalysts without metal particles for PS-AOPs still remains an important challenge. By coupling it with biomass waste reutilization, as highly desired in the environmental engineering, a step towards the “greening” of catalysis could be accomplished. In the present study, enhanced adsorption and persulfate-driven oxidation of 25 selected CECs were simultaneously achieved on single boron-doped carbocatalyst. A simple and green pyrolytic approach at 800°C was used to synthesize the boron-doped pyrochar using pinewood sawdust and boric acid. The obtained carbocatalyst was employed as metal-free activator of peroxydisulfate (PDS) for the degradation of 15 pesticides and 10 pharmaceutically active compounds (PhACs) in a water solution model mixture (30 µg/l concentration of each compound). Experimental results revealed that the introduction of boron moieties into the carbon network resulted in the creation of *adsorption/oxidation bifunctional material with enhanced surface affinity towards selected CECs and peroxydisulfate (PDS)*. *The adsorption positively promoted the subsequent oxidation with joint radical and non-radical pathway gaining very rapid and almost complete removal of 13 pesticides and all PhACs*. Due to high stability of boron sites, the tested carbocatalyst possesses a superior long-term durability enabling its use with real water matrices and in four consecutive cycles with similar efficiency. The aim of this study is to indicate possible directions for the development of cost-effective green catalysts with adequate activity and reuse stability which could be implemented in real industrial systems for the removal of CECs in the future.

Keywords: peroxydisulfate activation, pyrochar, B-doping, CECs

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POSTER PRESENTATION

UTILIZATION OF POULTRY WASTE AS A NATURAL BIOSORBENT FOR Cu²⁺ REMOVAL

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Over the past decade, the use of poultry waste in wastewater treatment processes for the removal of toxic metals via adsorption has attracted significant attention from researchers worldwide. The keratin proteins present in chicken feathers have proven to be highly effective in binding copper, iron, and chromium. The unique adsorption capability of keratin has sparked considerable interest in the potential use of chicken feathers as a biosorbent. In this study, the influence of contact time and adsorbent concentration on the adsorption of Cu²⁺ cations onto the adsorbent surface was investigated. The response variable observed was the percentage of adsorbed Cu²⁺ cations. The concentration of Cu²⁺ in the test solutions after the adsorption process was determined using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). Adsorption was monitored in both batch and ultrasonic systems for 60 minutes, at a defined shaking speed (150 rpm) and room temperature (298 K). Chicken feathers, with a specific surface area of the organic component ranging from 1 to 3 m² g⁻¹, proved to be a natural material suitable for isomorphic exchange with Cu²⁺ cations. During adsorption, the percentage of adsorbed copper cations increased with longer contact time. After one hour, chicken feathers exhibited higher Cu²⁺ adsorption in the ultrasonic system (73.7%) compared to the batch system (69.3%). These results provide a strong foundation for further research on systems designed for the removal of copper ions, aiming to reduce their toxic activity or eliminate their presence in environments where copper is undesirable.

Keywords: adsorption, chicken feathers, Cu²⁺ ions, biosorbent, ICP-OES

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POSTER PRESENTATION

BIOCATALYTIC PHENOL DEGRADATION USING PEROXIDASE EXTRACTED FROM CABBAGE LEAF RESIDUES

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The pursuit of sustainable and eco-friendly technologies for wastewater treatment is increasingly important to achieve global environmental objectives. Phenol, a hazardous and carcinogenic pollutant prevalent in industrial wastewater, requires efficient removal methods to protect human health and ecosystems. This study explores a novel biocatalytic approach for phenol degradation using peroxidase extracted from cabbage leaf residues (*Brassica oleracea*). The enzyme was isolated through simple buffer extraction and applied directly to phenol removal from aqueous solutions. The effects of various parameters, including phenol concentration, peroxidase concentration, hydrogen peroxide concentration, polyethylene glycol (PEG 300) concentration, incubation time, temperature, pH value, and stirring rate, were comprehensively evaluated to optimize removal efficiency. Optimal conditions for phenol removal (above 95%) were achieved with 3 mM phenol, 1 U·mL⁻¹ peroxidase, 3 mM hydrogen peroxide, 400 mg·L⁻¹ PEG, pH 7.0, temperature of 30°C, and stirring rate of 150 rpm after 120 minutes of incubation. These findings confirm that unpurified peroxidase isolated from cabbage leaf residues can effectively degrade phenol under these conditions, providing a cost-effective and environmentally friendly alternative to conventional enzyme sources. The proposed method also offers potential for industrial applications by significantly reducing the costs associated with enzyme purification. This study contributes to the advancement of green technologies aimed at addressing pollution challenges and developing bioreactors for phenol-contaminated wastewater treatment.

Keywords: phenol degradation, peroxidase, cabbage leaf residues, biocatalysis, wastewater treatment

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POSTER PRESENTATION

REMOVAL OF PHENOL FROM WATER USING ACTIVATED CARBON OBTAINED FROM *S. CEREVISIAE* BIOMASS

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In this study removal of phenol from water was carried out by using native and modified *S. cerevisiae* biomass, respectively. *S. cerevisiae* biomass was modified by an activation using K_2CO_3 and pyrolyzed at 500, 600, 700 and 800°C in tubular furnace and in an inert atmosphere. The activated carbon was characterized and its adsorption capacities for phenol removal were tested using batch adsorption process. Dimensions and morphology of the activated carbons were examined by scanning electron microscopy. The adsorbent-adsorbate contact time and the leaching of organic matter from the adsorbent were examined. The efficiency of phenol removal by native *S. cerevisiae* biomass was 3,6%. On the other side, the efficiency of phenol removal from aqueous solution was much higher of activated carbon obtained from *S. cerevisiae* biomass compared to native cells. The efficiency of phenol removal increased with increasing activation temperature of the activated carbons and ranged from 92.42% (sample obtained at 500°C) to 97.1% (sample obtained 800°C). Since, activated carbons obtained from *S. cerevisiae* yeast biomass in the temperature range 600-800°C had very similar adsorption capacities for phenol removal, further studies were conducted using activated carbon obtained from *S. cerevisiae* biomass at an activation temperature of 600°C. SEM micrograph of activated carbon obtained from *S. cerevisiae* biomass at an activation temperature of 600°C showed aggregates dimensions of 4-22 μm , while the dimensions of the cavities were in the range 0.4-1.2 μm essentially represented the dimensions of yeast cells. The efficiency of phenol adsorption using activated carbon occurs rapidly and equilibrium is achieved after 10 minutes contact. Therefore, the adsorption of phenol from water using activated carbon obtained from the biomass of the yeast *S. cerevisiae* is a fast process, with a high efficiency of phenol removal and no leaching of organic matter has not been determined from tested samples.

Keywords: *S. cerevisiae*, activated carbon, phenol removal, adsorption

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POSTER PRESENTATION

DEVELOPMENT OF A LOW-COST ZEOLITE COMPOSITE FILTER FOR ARSENIC REMOVAL FROM WATER

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There is a growing interest and expanding market for water filters both in industrial wastewater purification and in drinking water preparation sectors. Serbia and especially the Province of Vojvodina have a huge problem with the presence of arsenic in the drinking water which is considered a major issue and significant health risk for the population. In this study, a new zeolite filter enhanced with the addition of ferrite particles suitable for the removal of arsenic from the water was produced. The filter was produced by mixing the following components: zeolite 4A, bentonite, and kaolin in a ratio of 85:9:6. Dry mixing was performed in a planetary mill without balls for 60 minutes. 50% of water was added to the mixed mass of powder and a system was left to stand for a minimum of 24 hours before pressing to make the clay minerals stabilized, i.e. prevent swelling of bentonite after pressing. Further, drying in the oven was conducted to obtain a mass with a moisture content of 20-25% compared to the dry mass. Pressing was done at low pressures of 20-30 bar. The resulting mixture was baked at a temperature of 750°C with the exact heating mode set. After cooling, the obtained filter was used for further experiments.

The experiments were performed on a laboratory filtration device with a real water sample containing a high concentration of arsenic (148 µg/L). According to the obtained results, the tested membrane showed very good properties. The efficiency of arsenic removal from water was very good for the investigated sample (>98%). Results of this study indicated that tested materials have a great potential for the removal of arsenic from water, which makes them a promising low-cost and eco-friendly alternative to commercial materials. Further investigation should focus on the removal of other contaminants (heavy metals, emerging contaminants, etc), as well as the mechanical properties of the tested filter.

Keywords: zeolite, filters, arsenic, water treatment

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POSTER PRESENTATION

AGOSERV PROJECT – A UNIQUE PLATFORM FOR SUPPORTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS AND FOSTERING AGRO-ECOLOGICAL TRANSITION

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Agricultural systems, encompassing agroforestry, aquaculture, pastoralism, horticulture, and husbandry, are confronted with numerous interconnected challenges. The global population is projected to reach 9.7 billion by 2050, with a peak of nearly 11.2 billion by 2100. In this scenario, it is estimated that nearly the resources of three planets would be required to sustain current lifestyles. Within the current food and nutrition systems (FNS), the expanding global population will necessitate an increase in both crop and livestock production, which will likely lead to greater reliance on antibiotics, pesticides, and fertilizers. These practices can negatively affect soil functions and the broader ecosystem, potentially causing the emergence of pests and diseases. As a result, adapting current agricultural practices is no longer optional; it is critical not only for sustaining agricultural output but also for preserving essential ecosystem services. The scientific community plays a crucial role in supporting the shift towards agroecology by strengthening innovation in agricultural systems, emphasizing the integration of ecological processes to enhance the functioning of agro-ecosystems, and ultimately contributing to the development of sustainable food systems and supply chains. Research Infrastructures (RIs) possess the capability to offer long-term resources and services to research communities, positioning them uniquely to address these complex challenges and respond to this critical call. AgroServ project aims to integrate the full range of relevant RI capacities to facilitate a systemic and holistic approach. The primary mission of AgroServ is to support research and innovation by offering tailored and integrated RI services to advance sustainable and resilient agriculture, as well as to promote ecological transformation of agriculture. The AgroServ project provides to the European Research community with access to 143 innovative, customised, efficient RI services - physical, remote, virtual - from a multidisciplinary consortium of 12 RIs (life sciences, environmental sciences, social sciences) allowing to address all aspects of the transition to sustainable agriculture, its nexus with the environment, health and food security, including a better understanding of socio-economic implications. This will support research in agroecological transition, as well as the development of mitigation and adaptation strategies aimed at fostering a resilient and sustainable food system and the associated rural communities.

Keywords: agriculture, sustainable production, agroecosystems, transition, research infrastructure services

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POSTER PRESENTATION

SUSTAINABLE DAIRY INNOVATION THROUGH THE VALORIZATION OF SAGE (*SALVIA OFFICINALIS*) BY-PRODUCTS: TOWARD FUNCTIONAL FOODS

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Recent studies have intensively investigated the potential of utilizing plant-based by-products in the manufacture of functional dairy products. Fresh cheeses belong to the group of soft, unripened cheeses suitable for enhancement by functional ingredients. The aim of this study was to explore the possibility of valorizing sage (*Salvia officinalis*) by-products for the production of fresh cheese with enhanced biological activity and additional nutritional value. The research focused on the production of fresh cheese enriched with various sage-based ingredients with the goal of creating a novel functional product with specific technological characteristics and improved antioxidant potential.

Fresh cheese was produced using pasteurized cow's milk with 2.8% milk fat content. Inoculation was performed at 35 °C with the addition of a coagulation enzyme and a commercial starter culture (XPL-1). Different forms of sage were added after production at a concentration of 0.05 µL/g: sage essential oil, supercritical fluid extract, and ground sage herb. Milk acidification was monitored throughout the fermentation process. Cheese quality and yield were partially influenced by milk quality, the applied starter culture, and technological process parameters. The yield of fresh cheese was 18.19%. Regardless of sage addition, no significant differences were observed in dry matter or fat content either on the first or the last day of storage. Sage exhibited a positive effect on the antioxidant properties and total phenolic content, particularly when the herb form was used. Among samples enriched with sage, the highest measured values were observed in the sample containing ground sage herb after 30 days of storage. The highest total phenolic content was recorded in the sample with ground sage herb after 30 days of storage (1.92 ± 0.12 mg GAE/g). In all sage-enriched cheese samples, the DPPH values measured after production were higher than those in milk. The highest initial DPPH value was observed in the sample with sage herb at 3.94 ± 0.25 µM TE/g (day 0), while the maximum DPPH value reached 6.99 ± 0.34 µM TE/g after 30 days of storage. ABTS values were relatively similar among samples immediately after production, with slightly higher values in the sample containing sage herb at the end of storage 4.28 µM TE/g.

Based on the results, it can be concluded that the addition of sage in various forms increases the total phenolic content as well as FRAP, DPPH, and ABTS values in fresh cheese samples made with commercial starter cultures. This indicates that sage enhances the antioxidant properties of cheese regardless of the form used. Suggesting that the use of ground sage herb, may contribute to the production of functional cheeses with favorable sensory properties.

Keywords: fresh cheese, sage, antioxidative capacity

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POSTER PRESENTATION

ZnCrAl LDH BASED MIXED OXIDE AS PHOTOCATALYST FOR WASTEWATER REMEDIATION

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Environmental pollution, driven by the ongoing emergence of persistent and toxic pollutants, remains a critical global challenge due to its harmful impact on ecosystems and human health, thereby increasing the demand for sustainable materials for effective environmental remediation. Azo dyes, such as rhodamine B (RhB), brilliant cresyl blue (BCB), and methylene blue (MB) are significant sources of water pollution due to their widespread use in the chemical industry. Among various wastewater treatment methods (adsorption, ion-exchange, membrane filtration), photocatalysis has recently emerged as an efficient and eco-friendly process. Mixed metal oxides derived from layered double hydroxides, containing various metals (Zn, Al, Cr, Fe, Cu, etc.) have shown great potential as photocatalysts for the degradation of such pollutants in water mediums, due to their favorable photocatalytic and antimicrobial properties.

ZnCrAl layered double hydroxides were synthesized by low supersaturation coprecipitation method with metal content: Zn(II) 70mol.%; Cr(III) 5mol% and Al(III) mol%. To obtain mixed oxides the precipitates were dried (100°C, 12h) and calcined (500°C, 5h). The results of XRD analysis indicated that the thermal treatment initiated the collapse of the layered structure and the formation of the mixed oxide phase. Textural analysis revealed the formation of smaller mesopores after thermal treatment and slight increase in BET surface area (86 m²·g⁻¹) when compared to LDHs (69.7 m²·g⁻¹). Photocatalytic degradation of the test pollutants demonstrated high efficiency of the ZnCrAl mixed oxide, particularly in the removal of BCB (77%) and MB (56%) dye. In contrast, a comparatively lower degradation efficiency was observed for RhB solution, with 32% of the dye removed under the same conditions. The observed photocatalytic behavior can be attributed to differences in the structure and size of dye molecules, which influence their adsorption onto the active sites of the photocatalyst surface.

The results suggest that ZnCrAl mixed oxides have significant potential for future application in wastewater remediation.

Keywords: photocatalytic degradation, azo-dyes, semiconductors, wastewater treatment

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POSTER PRESENTATION

MERCURY EXPOSURE: EVIDENCE FROM A BIOMONITORING STUDY IN WOMEN UNDERGOING IN VITRO FERTILIZATION

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Having in mind the worldwide observed rising trend of infertility, *in vitro* fertilization (IVF), represents the typically applied assisted reproductive technology for the management of patients with fertility issues. Although the IVF success rate is strongly related to age of women, there is a growing interest in environmental factors that could be related to impaired female reproductive health and success of IVF cycle.

Previous studies suggested that exposure to metalloestrogens might be related to spontaneous abortion, irregular menstrual cycle and even infertility. Hence, the aim of this study was to evaluate the level of exposure to mercury among women undergoing IVF.

In this cross-sectional study 50 women between the ages of 18-45 with preserved ovarian function were included. The recruitment was conducted on voluntary bases at the Special Gynecological Hospital "Genesis", Serbia. Mercury was analyzed in the first morning urine sample after microwave digestion using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry.

Being recognized as an endocrine disruptor, mercury was measured in 60% urine samples (30 out of 50) above the limit of quantification (1.9 µg/L). The obtained average concentration (8.98±11.68 µg/L) in this study was more than two times higher than the 95th percentile urinary value reported in a nation-wide sample of Spanish women (3.99 µg/L). In addition, the average concentration significantly suppressed the urine mercury measurements in pregnant women within National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey in USA (geometric mean 0.25 µg/L). The obtained results indicate that women undergoing IVF in Serbia are long-term exposed to mercury. Based on the literature data the consumption of contaminated fish might be considered as the major source of exposure. The associations of mercury exposure with IVF outcomes require further examination.

Keywords: ICP-MS, environmental pollution, urine, fertility

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POSTER PRESENTATION

BIODEGRADABLE PROTEIN-BASED FILMS INCORPORATED WITH RUTIN AND RUTIN/ β -CYCLODEXTRIN COMPLEX

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With increase in plastic material production and use, many environmental problems have arisen. One of the approaches to decrease plastic consumption is replacing it with biodegradable materials such as proteins. Gelatin type A and sodium-caseinate, both proteins of animal origin, when in certain mass ratio can interact electrostatically in solution and form complex coacervates. These coacervates have different properties compared to proteins individually and can be used to form films via casting method, with addition of plasticizer. Rutin and its inclusion complex with β -cyclodextrin were incorporated in these films and their influence on optical, mechanical and barrier properties of films was investigated. Inclusion complexes were prepared by kneading method and characterized using ATR FTIR and thermal analyses (TGA and DSC). Decreased intensity and changes in characteristic peaks on ATR FTIR spectrum, as well as different thermal behavior confirm inclusion complex formation. With addition of rutin and its inclusion complexes to gelatin/sodium-caseinate films thickness and opacity increased with increase in rutin concentration. Solubility and water vapor permeability of films in water decreased with rutin addition and increased with inclusion complex addition, most likely because of low solubility of rutin in water, and increased solubility when in complex. Films with rutin showed decrease in tensile strength and slight decrease in elongation at break while films with inclusion complexes showed increase in tensile strength and decrease in elongation at break, compared to films without active substance. Rutin was extracted from films in 50% ethanol and the amount of rutin extracted from films with inclusion complexes was higher, probably due to increase in rutin solubility in water when complexed. It can be concluded that both rutin and its inclusion complex with β -cyclodextrin were successfully incorporated in protein films which have potential use in production of packaging materials or single-use cosmetics (for example face masks or pimple patches), because of rutin's high antioxidant activity.

Keywords: biodegradable films, protein films, rutin, cyclodextrin complexes

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POSTER PRESENTATION

THE INFLUENCE OF KOMBUCHA INOCULUM ON ACIDIFICATION PROCESS, QUALITY OF FRESH CHEESE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY OF PRODUCTION

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Fresh cheeses are produced by coagulating milk, cream, or whey using acid, a combination of acid and rennet, or acid and heat. The composition of the milk and the type of starter culture influence the technological process, the structure and stability of the final product. Starter culture may play a crucial role in fresh cheese production, contributing to the acidification process, development of organoleptic properties through their metabolic activity, and affect fermentation time, energy consumption, and, thereby, affect environmental sustainability of cheese production processes.

This study investigated the feasibility of producing fresh cheese using a non-conventional kombucha inoculum in comparison with a commercial starter culture (FD DVS XPL-1, Chr. Hansen A/S, Denmark). The effects. The goal was to assess how selected starter cultures affect the acidification process, sensory characteristics, as well as textural and rheological properties of the fresh cheese and environmental sustainability of cheese production processes.

The results revealed significant differences in the acidification dynamics, physical characteristics, and sensory properties between the cheese samples. The fermentation process proceeded more rapidly in the sample produced with the kombucha inoculum than in the one made with the commercial XPL-1 starter culture. The cheese made with XPL-1 exhibited a typical mild aroma and smooth texture, whereas the cheese produced with the kombucha inoculum showed a specific taste and flavor, along with a grainier texture. Notably, the firmness of the kombucha-inoculated cheese sample (4168 g) was significantly greater than that of the cheese made with the commercial starter culture (675 g). Over a 10-day storage period, the structural changes in the kombucha cheese were more pronounced than in the control sample.

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the use of kombucha inoculum influences the fermentation time during the technological process, and environmental sustainability of fresh cheese production, and alters the structural and sensory characteristics of the final product. Future research will focus on enriching kombucha-based fresh cheese with functional ingredient to further enhance its nutritional and sensory value.

Keywords: fresh cheese, kombucha inoculum, acidification process, quality, environmental sustainability

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POSTER PRESENTATION

INSECT FARMING BYPRODUCTS AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOURCE OF CHITOSAN

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The growing interest in natural raw materials, healthy lifestyles, and environmental protection has led to increased attention toward biopolymers in recent years. Chitosan is a biopolymer derived from chitin, the second most abundant natural polymer. Traditionally, chitin and chitosan have been commercially obtained from crustaceans. However, due to the growing market demand for these substances, it has become essential to identify alternative sources. One promising option is the extraction of chitin from insects, whose exoskeletons are rich in this polymer. In recent years, insects have been increasingly bred for various purposes, with *Tenebrio molitor* being one of the most commonly cultivated species, primarily for protein extraction. Its life cycle includes multiple molting events, resulting in the production of chitin-rich exuviae. These exuviae, typically considered waste, represent a potentially sustainable and underutilized source for the production of chitin and chitosan. In this study, chitosan was extracted from the larval exuviae of *T. molitor*. The raw material was assessed through the yield of extracted chitin and subsequently derived chitosan. The obtained chitosan was characterized by determining its degree of deacetylation and viscosity-average molecular weight, analyzed using FTIR spectroscopy and compared to commercially available chitosan, as well as by observing surface morphology through SEM analysis. In this study, the chitin yield from *T. molitor* larval exuviae, following demineralization and deproteinization, was 12.86% relative to the initial dry biomass. After the deacetylation process, a chitosan yield of 7.41% was obtained. The results demonstrated that this source yields chitosan with favorable physicochemical properties, including a degree of deacetylation of 72.27% and viscosity-average molecular weight of 612 kDa. Chitosan with such characteristics offers potential for a wide range of applications, including production of biodegradable films, controlled-release systems, and other biotechnological uses.

Keywords: chitosan, extraction, T. molitor

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POSTER PRESENTATION

BORON-DOPED BIOCHAR AS AN EFFICIENT ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL OF SELECTED CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN FROM WASTEWATER

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Contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) are increasingly being released into the environment as an unintended consequence of global population growth and industrial activity. As environmental standards become more stringent, there is an urgent need to develop and implement innovative and efficient treatment technologies. Adsorption on activated carbon is a widely used technology that can partially remove CECs from wastewater. Still, it is expensive due to the high production costs of AC and its possible nonrenewable resource origin. Therefore, low-cost materials, including biochar, have been investigated as a potential substitute for activated carbon. In the present study, adsorption of 4 selected CECs (3 synthetic hormones – progesterone, 17- α -ethinylestradiol, and β -estradiol and 1 antibiotic – levofloxacin) was simultaneously achieved on single boron-doped biochar. A simple and green pyrolytic approach at 800°C was applied to produce the boron-doped biochar using pinewood sawdust and boric acid. The obtained biochar was employed for the adsorption of selected CECs in a water solution model mixture (500 μ g/L concentration of each compound) with a dose of 1 g/L. Samples were taken at time points 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, and 60 min, and the residual concentrations of CECs were measured using the HPLC-DAD-FLD method. The applied boron-doped adsorbent proved exceptionally effective for the removal of progesterone and levofloxacin, as they were eliminated from the system after 5 min. In contrast, the adsorption process of 17- α -ethinylestradiol and β -estradiol was slower, with an efficiency of 99% and 60% after 60 min, respectively. The obtained results indicate that the tested boron-doped adsorbent possesses high adsorptive potential for the simultaneous removal of selected CECs from water implying its prospect for the implementation in scaled-up systems. The results and the demonstrated efficiency of biochar in removing selected CECs suggest that further research should focus on evaluating its implementation on a larger scale for the treatment of real wastewater.

Keywords: boron-doped biochar, adsorption, CECs, wastewater

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POSTER PRESENTATION

AFLATOXINS IN SERBIAN MAIZE: THE URGENT NEED FOR INTEGRATED RESPONSES TO CLIMATE CHANGE

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The Republic of Serbia has faced escalating climate change in the last two decades, contributing to a substantial rise in mycotoxin contamination, particularly aflatoxins in maize – its most widely cultivated crop. Climate change in Serbia is characterized by rising air temperatures, an increased number of tropical days, more frequent heatwaves, and prolonged drought periods. Aflatoxins, toxic secondary metabolites produced by *Aspergillus* species, represent a growing serious challenge both in Serbia and globally, with their prevalence rising significantly due to changing climatic conditions. As some of the most toxic naturally occurring contaminants, aflatoxins pose a serious threat to both human and animal health.

Over the past 16 years (2009–2024), aflatoxins have been detected at concerning frequencies, ranging from 24% to 84% across eight different years. Notably, higher contamination frequencies were observed in 2012, 2013, 2015, and 2017, all marked by hot and dry summer months. Particularly alarming is the period from 2021 to 2024, during which contamination levels consistently exceeded 60%. This trend poses serious long-term threats to food and feed safety and security, as aflatoxin contamination in maize leads to their transfer throughout the production chain into milk, dairy products, and various feedstuffs, resulting in significant health concerns and substantial economic losses. This situation raises pressing concerns, given that Serbia ranks among the leading maize producers and exporters in both Europe and the global market. Recurring aflatoxin contamination has not only caused major economic losses but also damaged the country's reputation as a reliable supplier to European and international markets. Climate projections, along with our findings and those from other studies, indicate that research efforts alone are insufficient to address the growing threat of aflatoxins in Serbian maize. Therefore, maize control strategies and management practices must be substantially enhanced through: a) urgent multidisciplinary collaboration among researchers, government, producers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers; b) targeted investment in monitoring systems, climate-resilient agriculture, and stricter regulatory enforcement; and; c) comprehensive education across the entire food chain-from farmers adopting best practices to consumers demanding safe products.

Keywords: aflatoxins, climate change, maize

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POSTER PRESENTATION

REMOVAL OF BISPHENOL A FROM WATER: CARBON-BASED ADSORBENTS, MECHANISMS, AND TREATMENT EFFICIENCY

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Bisphenol A is a synthetic compound in plastics and resins, commonly found in food packaging and consumer products. Due to widespread use and poor disposal, it accumulates in the environment and the human body, disrupting hormonal balance and causing health issues in humans and aquatic organisms. Several methods have been developed for bisphenol A removal, such as membrane technologies, and advanced oxidation processes showing high efficiency, among which adsorption is the most commonly applied. This review provides an overview of recent advancements in bisphenol A removal from water using adsorption, highlighting the effectiveness of carbon-based materials and the potential of tailored adsorbent design for sustainable water treatment.

Adsorption is a cost-effective and scalable solution, with research focused on enhancing carbon-based adsorbents, such as activated carbon, carbon nanotubes, and graphene-based composites. Their performance depends on the specific surface area, porosity, and the presence of appropriate functional groups on the surface of the adsorbent, enabling interactions with pollutants such as hydrogen bonding, π - π stacking, and electrostatic attraction. Activated carbon is a well-established adsorbent for water treatment recognized for its ability to remove persistent organic pollutants. Recent studies have highlighted the impressive performance of various carbon-based adsorbents designed to target bisphenol A under diverse conditions. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes modified with iron oxide and manganese dioxide, for instance, achieved 99% removal efficiency within 150 min and were reusable for at least six cycles with a capacity of 132.9 mg/g. A composite of calcium alginate and activated carbon demonstrated an even higher capacity of 368.3 mg/g and stable performance across six cycles, though it required up to 50 h to reach equilibrium [3]. Utilization of nitrogen-doped carbon achieved a high bisphenol A adsorption capacity of 1351 mg/g and rapid removal within 5 min [1,2]. These findings emphasize the potential of advanced adsorbent engineering to enhance bisphenol A removal across diverse water treatment scenarios.

[1] Sun, Z., Zhao, L., Liu, C., Zhen, Y., & Ma, J. (2020). Fast adsorption of BPA with high capacity based on π - π electron donor-acceptor and hydrophobicity mechanism using an in-situ sp^2 C dominant nitrogen-doped carbon. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 381, 122510.

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Keywords: adsorption, bisphenol A, water treatment

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POSTER PRESENTATION

POTENTIAL OF LIGNIN AS AN ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL AND DETECTION OF HORMONES FROM WATER

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The occurrence of hormones in aquatic environments has become a significant environmental concern. Their presence in water bodies may pose risks to aquatic organisms and human health. Monitoring of these contaminants is crucial for assessing exposure and potential risks, and one effective approach involves the use of passive samplers, which enable continuous monitoring over extended periods.

In this study, the potential of lignin as a sorbent for hormones was evaluated through batch adsorption experiments. A synthetic mixture containing approximately 500 µg/L of hormones was prepared as model water. 50 mL of the model solution was mixed with either 60 mg or 200 mg of kraft lignin derived from nutshells for up to 72 hours. Samples (1 mL) were taken at 24, 48, and 72 hours. The initial and residual concentrations of β -estradiol and α -ethinylestradiol in water solutions before and after the contact with lignin were determined using HPLC-DAD/FL.

Lignin demonstrated relatively slow adsorption for β -estradiol, with similar adsorption efficiencies (68%) observed for both lignin doses after 24 hours. Equilibrium was reached after 48 hours, with an adsorption efficiency of 81%. In contrast, α -ethinylestradiol showed higher adsorption efficiency, reaching 80% for the 60 mg dose and 89% for the 200 mg dose after 24 hours. Maximum adsorption of 90% and 95%, respectively was achieved after 48 hours. However, prolonged contact time (72 hours) slightly decreased adsorption in both cases.

Moreover, given its proven adsorption capacity, lignin was further evaluated for potential integration into passive samplers by subjecting the saturated material to extraction. To fulfill the role of passive samplers in monitoring natural water resources, the extraction process must enable quantitative and reproducible isolation of previously adsorbed hormones, so that the concentration of relevant pollutants can be accurately determined in the resulting extract. The lignin was packed into an empty cartridge between two frit discs, and methanol was used as the elution solvent. However, the resulting eluate was colored and contained fine particles, making it unsuitable for HPLC analysis. Since methanol proved ineffective for eluting the adsorbed hormones, alternative solvents should be tested to determine the suitability of lignin for use in passive samplers.

Keywords: adsorption, lignin, hydrochar, hormones, passive samplers

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POSTER PRESENTATION

CROSS-BORDER COOPERATION FOR SUSTAINABLE CANCER RESEARCH: THE DAADRAC PROJECT EXPERIENCE

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The DAADRAC project (Development of Anticancer Agents for Drug-Resistant Cancers) exemplifies how sustainable, interdisciplinary, and cross-border research can address some of the most pressing biomedical challenges. Within the framework of the Interreg IPA Cross-border Cooperation Programme Croatia–Serbia, researchers from Serbia and Croatia have joined forces to combat cancer therapy resistance through innovative chemical and biological approaches.

DAADRAC utilizes the complementary expertise of teams from Novi Sad and Osijek to tackle the wicked problem of cancer, with a particular focus on drug-resistant forms. In this presentation, we share findings on bile acid-derived steroidal compounds capable of modulating the NRF2 signaling axis, a key regulator of oxidative stress and drug resistance in tumors. A core component of the project is also the emphasis on fostering young researchers, promoting interdisciplinary scientific communication, and enabling joint planning, all of which contribute to regional research excellence and capacity building.

This presentation will highlight not only the scientific progress of the project, but also the importance of sustainable, cross-border collaboration in advancing biomedical research solutions.

Keywords: anticancer, drug-resistant cancers, NRF2 modulation, cross-border cooperation, sustainability

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POSTER PRESENTATION

ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF VISIBLE LIGHT DRIVEN PHOTOCATALYTIC CERAMIC BASED NANO-COMPOSITES

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The aim of this research was to develop a pure visible light driven photocatalytic suspension which can be applied onto interior walls and wall paints in order to invent an efficient self-cleaning solution for inner spaces. Ceramic based nano-composite layered double hydroxides carrying the metal-doped TiO₂ suspensions were synthesized using a modified low supersaturation co-precipitation route.

Detailed material characterization studies by means of scanning and transmission electron microscopy (SEM/TEM), thermogravimetry (TG), dynamic scanning calorimetry (DSC), as well as microstructure analysis by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) were performed.

The photocatalytic self-cleaning properties of the optimally synthesized photocatalytic suspension were assessed when applied on mineral wall substrates after having been illuminated only with white LED visible light. Finally, the antibacterial activity of newly developed visible light driven photocatalytic ceramic based nano-composites was proven at several antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains.

Keywords: nano-composites, photocatalysis, self-cleaning, antibacterial activity

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About TwINSol-CECs Project

TwINSol-CECs will generate the collaborative environment required for University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad (TFNS), Serbia, to increase and implement its research in the field of CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN (CECs). This will be accomplished by twinning under Horizon Europe programme with two EU research intensive institutions with strong expertise in the field:

- Spanish National Research Council, Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research (CSIC), Barcelona, Spain, and
- NOVA University Lisbon, NOVA School of Science and Technology (UNL), Lisbon, Portugal,

which eminent researchers will help TFNS to unlock the scientific potential through intensive networking, transfer of knowledge and technical expertise.

Surveillance of CECs and improvement of the removal technologies have important role in protection of humans and the environmental resources. Such efforts are in compliance with the European Green Deal (EGD) commitment for transition of EU to zero-pollution, toxic free environment. They are also in line with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Preserving the quality of water, air, and soil, protecting the drinking water sources, and promotion of the water protection, and pollution reduction from the source to tap, are among the priority actions of EU Strategy for the Danube Region.

TFNS recognized the Twinning Western Balkans call under HORIZON EUROPE programme of European Union as an opportunity to reinforce own capacities already proven in innovative CECs analysis and removal methodologies and to strengthen its position in the European Research Area. The project answered the call requirements, and it was evaluated with 14.5 out of 15. It started on August 01, 2022 and will last 3 years. The project maximum grant is 1 432 937.50 Euros. The full project name is "TWINNING FOR ENHANCING THE SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE OF FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY NOVI SAD FOR INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT ENVIRONMENTAL RESOURCES FROM CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN".

The project represents a coherent set of knowledge, skills, experience, and awareness raising activities, dissemination, communication, networking, coordination, etc. for successful achieving of the project objectives.

More about the project with the latest news on project activities and events may be found at the project web site www.twinsol-cecs.com